

Cholula (Tollan Cholollan Tlachihualtépetl)

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Entry tags: Sacred mountain, Temple, Mesoamerican Religions, Archaeological Site, Religious Group, Otomanguan, Mesoamerica, Uto-Aztecan, Language, Religious Place, Early populations of Mexico, Religious Complex

Cholula, known as Tollan Cholollan Tlachihualtépetl upon the arrival of the Hispanic in 1519, is the most outstanding pre-Hispanic city in the Mexican Highlands and constitutes a very ancient place with continuous occupation from about 2,500 years ago to the present. Cholula is located in the Puebla-Tlaxcala Valley region and its natural environment has always been quite beneficial for human habitation. According to existing archaeological evidence in the area, the first farming villages were settled since 900 BC. Around 100 CE, after a massive volcanic eruption of the Popocatepetl volcano, the former village in the area became the main urban center of the valley. Its monumental ceremonial precinct or acropolis (Great Pyramid of Cholula or Tlachihualtépetl) expanded several times during the following centuries until its abandonment in the 6th century. After a time of social decline, the city was repopulated and conquered by foreign groups like the Olmeca-Xicalanca (900-1150 CE) and the Tolteca-Chichimeca (1150-1350 CE). By this time, the famous Temple of Quetzalcoatl was built on the outskirts of the ancient acropolis where a new center for power and religious cult was founded. Many ancient documents, chronicles, and codices mention Cholula as a city where important historical and mythical events occurred in the centuries prior to the arrival of the Hispanics in 1519 CE. Cholula was recognized as a politically autonomous and sacred city with economic splendor, and was an obligatory pilgrimage destination for many distant communities because of its political, religious, and economic prestige in Mesoamerica.

Date Range: 900 BCE - 1519 CE

Region: Cholula

Region tags: Mexico, Puebla-Tlaxcala Valley, Mesoamerica, Central Mexican Highlands

Map: Cholula settlement at its population peak (350-450 CE). The area occupied by pre-Hispanic Cholula has been part of a very fertile region with many rivers, streams, and springs, and in addition, it has deep, nutrient-rich soils formed over the last millennia by the transport of edaphic materials from the surrounding mountains. Therefore, its natural environment has always been quite beneficial for human habitation. The area is located in the Puebla-Tlaxcala Valley region, a wide plain with an average altitude of 2160 meters above sea level. The valley is located in the Central Mexican Highlands surrounded by the Sierra Nevada with several peaks or natural elevations of volcanic origin, standing out the colossi such as Popocatepetl, Iztaccíhuatl, Matlalcueye and Pico de Orizaba, with heights of more than 4000 meters above sea level.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Uruñuela y Ladrón de Guevara, Gabriela, Patricia Plunket Nagoda y Amparo Robles Salmerón (2009). Cholula: Art and Architecture of an Archetypal City. In "The Art of Urbanism: How Mesoamerican Kingdoms Represented Themselves in Architecture and Imagery.", ed. by William L. Fash and Leonardo López Luján, pp. 135-171. *Dumbarton Oaks*: Washington DC.
- Source 2: Uruñuela, Gabriela, Patricia Plunket, and María Amparo Robles (2013). Building the Tlachihualtépetl: The Social and Ideological Foundations of the Great Pyramid of Cholula, Mexico. In "Constructing, Deconstructing, and Reconstructing Social Identity: 2,000 Years of Monumentality in Teotihuacan and Cholula, Mexico", ed. by Saburo Sugiyama, Shigeru Kabata, Tomoko Taniguchi and Etsuko Niwa, pp. 95-106. *Cultural Symbiosis Research Institute, Aichi Prefectural University*: Aichi.
- Source 1: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara (2018). "Cholula". *Fondo de Cultura Económica, El Colegio de México and Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas*: Mexico City.
- Source 2: Solís, Felipe, Gabriela Uruñuela, Patricia Plunket, Martín Cruz y Dionisio Rodríguez (eds.)

- (2006). "Cholula: The Great Pyramid". CONACULTA, INAH and Editorial Azabache: Mexico City.
- Source 3: *Arqueología Mexicana* (2012). Cholula: La ciudad sagrada. "Arqueología Mexicana" Vol. XX(115).
- Source 1: de Rojas, Gabriel (1984). Relación de Cholula. In "Relaciones Geográficas del Siglo XVI: Tlaxcala", Vol. 2, ed. René Acuña. UNAM: México, D. F.
- Source 2: Dumond, Don and Florencia Müller (1972). Classic to Postclassic in Highland Central Mexico. "Science" 175: 1208-1215.
- Source 3: Marquina, Ignacio (1970). "Proyecto Cholula", coord. Ignacio Marquina, pp. 31-45. Serie de Investigaciones No. 19. INAH: México, D. F.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://mediateca.inah.gob.mx/repositorio/islandora/object/guia%3A258>
- Source 1 Description: Guide to the archaeological site of Cholula, Puebla, México.
- Source 2 URL: <https://americae.fr/en/papers/secuencias-performativas-destruccion-ritual-esculturas-mesoamerica-cacaxtla/>
- Source 2 Description: Article about ritual destruction of sculptures in Cacaxtla, Xochicalco and Cholula during the Epiclassic (600 to 900 AD)
- Source 3 URL: <https://pueblosoriginarios.com/meso/valle/tolteca/anales.html>
- Source 3 Description: Summary and images of the post-Hispanic codex "Historia Tolteca Chichimeca"
- Source 1 URL: https://lugares.inah.gob.mx/es/zonas-arqueologicas/zonas/1776-cholula.html?lugar_id=1776
- Source 1 Description: Portal with general and practical information about the archaeological site.
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.famsi.org/reports/02042/02042Plunket01.pdf>
- Source 2 Description: Report about the "Dating Cholula" project, designed to develop an independent chronological sequence for Cholula.
- Source 3 URL: <https://revistas.inah.gob.mx/index.php/antropologia/article/view/2941/2842>
- Source 3 Description: Article about archaeological investigations at Cholula, Puebla, México.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

> Type of excavation:

– Scientific

> Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1931-Present

Reference: SEP, Secretaría de Educación Pública. Monumentos Arqueológicos De México. México: Talleres Gráficos de la Nación, 1933.

> Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: UDLAP Archaeological Research (1968-2019)

Notes: Another important group of contributions to Cholula archeology for the understanding of the pre-Hispanic development of the settlement was a series of projects linked to the University of the Americas Puebla (UDLAP). These research, survey and rescue projects were carried out on the UDLAP campus (and in some properties outside) from the moment before its construction (1968) and throughout the life of the university, because of infrastructure modifications and construction of new buildings, which were supervised until the year 2019, when the Archaeology area was officially closed. These investigations were directed and/or supervised by Daniel Wolfman, Joseph Mountjoy, David Peterson, Michael Lind, Norberto González, Patricia Plunket, Gabriela Uruñuela, Gilda Hernández, Juan Albaítero, Aurelio López, Natalia Mauricio and Manuel Vera. Joseph Mountjoy in 1971 and later by Teresa Salomón in 2005 carried out other important investigations on the Cerro Zapotecas, on the outskirts of Cholula. They shed light on a poorly understood period in Cholula: the transition from the Classic to the Postclassic. Likewise, the excavations carried out by Patricia Plunket and Gabriela Uruñuela between 1993 and 1994, in the nuns' house of the Convent of San Gabriel, made it possible to obtain archaeological data from the area directly associated with the Great Plaza where the Temple of Quetzalcóatl was expected to be located. Likewise, all the academic work derived from the analysis of the information obtained in these excavations, including several undergraduate and graduate theses, provided very valuable contributions to the understanding

of pre-Hispanic Cholula.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Mountjoy, Joseph, and David Peterson. "man and Land at Prehispanic Cholula. Publications in Anthropology, No. 4. Nashville: Vanderbilt University, 1973.

Reference: Peterson, David. "The Real Cholula". *Notas Mesoamericanas* 10 (1987): 71-118.

Reference: Mountjoy, Joseph B. "La Caída Del Clásico En Cholula Visto Desde El Cerro Zapotecas". In *El Auge Y La Caída Del Clásico En El México Central*, edited by Joseph B. Mountjoy and Donald L. Brockington, 237-58. México: UNAM, 1987.

Reference: Plunket, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela. "Antecedentes Prehispánicos". In *Cholula, Un Vínculo De Sabiduría Y Fraternidad*, 19-28. Cholula: UDLA Publicaciones, 2002.

Reference: Salomón, Teresa, Elba Domínguez, and Gabriela Uruñuela. "Vasos Y Braseros, Cerámicas Y Rituales Del Clásico En Cholula.". In *Migración, Población, Territorio Y Cultura. Homenaje a Román Piña Chan*, edited by Julieta Aréchiga. México: SMA, IIA, UNAM, 2006.

Reference: Salomón Salazar, María Teresa. "Nuevos Datos Para Entender La Transición Del Clásico Al Posclásico En El Cerro Zapotecas". *Arqueología* 43 (2010): 99-114.
<https://revistas.inah.gob.mx/index.php/arqueologia/article/view/3457>.

Reference: Salomón Salazar, María Teresa. "¿conflictos Étnicos O Arqueológicos? Una Reevaluación De La Evidencia Cerámica Del Valle De Puebla-tlaxcala Durante Del Epiclásico". *Ollin (centro Regional INAH Veracruz)* 10 (2012): 35-43.

Reference: López, Aurelio, and Gabriela Uruñuela. "Capacidad De Almacenamiento En Pozos Troncocónicos De Cholula, Puebla.". In *Memorias Del Simposio Internacional "arqueología De Almacenamiento En Tiempos Prehispánicos Desde El Norte De México Hasta El Altiplano Central*, edited by Véronique Darras, Séverine Bortot, and Dominique Michelet. México: CEMCA, Universidad de San Luis Potosí, Université de Paris 1, 2012.

Reference: McCafferty, Geoffrey. "The Ceramic and Chronology of Cholula, Mexico". *Ancient Mesoamerica* 7 (1996): 299-323.

Reference: Collegian. "Pyramid and Multiple Burials Discovered at Excavations". University of the Americas Collegian, 1968.
http://catarina.udlap.mx/ximg/db/xmlibris/sala_de_archivos_y_colecciones_especiales/fondo_moderno/periodicos_universitarios/

Reference: Torres Porras, Alicia. *La Transición Del Posclásico Tardío a La Colonia Temprana: El Caso Del Convento De San Gabriel De Cholula.* Cholula: Unpublished bachelor thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2019.

—Official or descriptive name: Proyecto Cholula (1931-1971)

Notes: Ignacio Marquina was the director the Proyecto Cholula; his team carried out the archaeological explorations of the huge mound of the Great Pyramid of Cholula through the excavation of more than 10 km of tunnels that exposed the contours of the structures inside. The explorations began in 1931 in the northeastern sector of the mound, because the rain and wind had eroded its surface and some architectural features were exposed. Subsequently, due to the architectural complexity of that area, they decided to excavate two main tunnels that cut the mound north-south and east-west. These central tunnels branched into secondary tunnels over different fronts or facades of the inner structures, showing that the mound was formed by the overlapping and attaching of many buildings. Excavations were also carried out on the exterior of the sides of the monument to study material remains such as ceramics and lithics that would allow defining the periods of occupation of the site. On the south side, during the final part of the project, large areas with plazas and buildings were investigated through extensive open excavations; consolidation and reconstruction works were also carried out so that the site could become an archaeological zone that people could visit. The Proyecto Cholula had a comprehensive anthropological approach and covered other areas such as physical anthropology, ethnography, history, zoobotany and geology, where personalities such as Jorge Acosta, Ponciano Salazar, Eduardo Contreras, Carlos Hernández, Zaid Lagunas, Sergio López, Eduardo Matos, Miguel Messmacher, Florencia Müller, Eduardo Noguera, Javier Romero, Carlos Serrano, among others participated.

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio, ed.. *Proyecto Cholula*. Edited by Ignacio Marquina. Serie De Investigaciones No.19. México: INAH, 1970.

Reference: SEP, Secretaría de Educación Pública. *Monumentos Arqueológicos De México*. México: Talleres Gráficos de la Nación, 1933.

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio . *Aquitectura Prehispánica*. Memorias Del INAH No.1. México: INAH, 1951.

Reference: Noguera, Eduardo. *La Cerámica Arqueológica De Cholula*. México: Editorial Guaranía, 1954.

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio . "Cholula, Puebla". In *Los Pueblos Y Señoríos Teocráticos: El*

Periodo De Las Ciudades Urbanas, Primera Parte, edited by Eduardo Matos, 109–22. México: SEP, INAH, 1975.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. Motivación Y Cambio Culturales: Los Orígenes De La Gran Pirámide De Cholula.. Cholula: Unpublished bachelor thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2007.

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio . "Exploraciones En La Pirámide De Cholula, Pue.". In Vigésimo Congreso Internacional De Americanistas. Actas De La Primera Sesión, Celebrada En La Ciudad De México En 1939. México: INAH-SEP, 1939.

Reference: Matos Moctezuma, Eduardo. "Introducción". In Cholula, the Great Pyramid, 13–16. México: CONACULTA, INAH and Grupo Azabache, 2006.

Reference: Messmacher, Miguel, ed.. Cholula Informe Preliminar. Edited by Miguel Messmacher. México: Nueva Arqueología, 1967.

– Official or descriptive name: INAH Salvage and Research Archaeological Projects

Notes: After the Proyecto Cholula, most of the archaeological explorations in Cholula have been excavations derived from archaeological salvages or rescues in response to civil works carried out in the modern city. In general, these surveys are planned to obtain samples of materials to understand the human occupation sequence in the area. Also, their goal is to document the existence or absence of structures or cultural features that could be affected by those civil public works (like any construction project for electrical, telephone or drainage infrastructure) or private projects (estate building or remodeling like houses, malls o or any commercial places). The Archeology Area of the Centro INAH Puebla carries out these explorations.

Reference: Romero Butrón, Ashuni, and Carlos Cedillo Ortega. "Excavando En Las Calles De Cholula: El Reto Del Progreso.". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 74–75.

Reference: Suárez Cruz, Sergio, and Silvia Martínez Arriaga. "Breve Historia De La Arqueología De Cholula, Puebla.". *Antropología. Revista Interdisciplinaria Del INAH* 78 (2005): 87–94.

– Official or descriptive name: Proyecto Tetimpa (2003-2013) and Dating Cholula project (2005)

Notes: The goal of the Proyecto Tetimpa, co-directed by Dr. Patricia Plunket y Dr. Gabriela Uruñuela, was to address the effects of the eruptive events documented in Tetimpa (an ancient village on the foot plains of the Popocatepetl volcano) on the socio-historical development of Cholula as a line of research. The major aim was to explore the possible link between the volcanic eruption in the first century AD and the beginnings of the monumental architecture in Cholula, as a political-religious response to the ecological, social, political, economic and ideological conflicts resulting from this natural disaster. Because the construction sequence published by the Proyecto Cholula was schematic and often contradictory, the Proyecto Tetimpa decided to create a detailed digital 3D map of the tunnels excavated by the Proyecto Cholula and the exposed architecture inside the mound of the Great Pyramid. Furthermore, the Dating Cholula project, also by Patricia Plunket and Gabriela Uruñuela, focused on dating the earliest construction phases of the Great Pyramid, in order to provide a more reliable chronological framework.

Reference: Plunket, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela. "Preclassic Household Patterns Preserved Under Volcanic Ash at Tetimpa, Puebla, Mexico". *Latin American Antiquity* 9, no. 4 (December 1998). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3537029>.

Reference: Plunket, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela. "Dating Cholula", 2005. <http://www.famsi.org/reports/02042/section01.htm>.

Reference: Uruñuela, Gabriela, Patricia Plunket, and María Amparo Robles. "Cholula: Art and Architecture of an Archetypal City.". In *The Art of Urbanism: How Mesoamerican Kingdoms Represented Themselves in Architecture and Imagery.*, edited by William L. Fash and Leonardo López Luján, 135–71. Washington DC: Dumbarton Oaks, 2009.

Reference: Gabriela, Uruñuela, and María Amparo Robles. "Las Subestructuras De La Gran Pirámide De Cholula: Viejos Túneles, Nueva Tecnología, Nuevos Datos". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 36–41.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 0 CE - 600 CE

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

—Other [specify]: Popocatepetl and Iztaccíhuatl volcanoes

Notes: Popocatepetl (5,380 meters above sea level) and Iztaccíhuatl (5,215 meters above sea level) are peaks of volcanic origin that frame the western horizon of the Puebla-Tlaxcala Valley.

Reference: INEGI. "Elevaciones Y Relieve", 2021.

https://cuentame.inegi.org.mx/mapas/pdf/nacional/relieve/elevaciones_relieve-n.pdf.

—Water source

—Other [specify]: Reed Place, and Ahuejote and/or white willow

Notes: "Tollan Cholollan" is a Nahuatl name. The first term literally means "Reed Place", but it is not a descriptive title but an honorific one; at the time of the Conquest, the title of "Tollan" was prefixed to the names of important cities. On the other hand, the meaning of "Cholollan" has provoked debate among scholars. The verb "cholloa" means to flee, to run or to jump or to settle down; the word "achololan" means "where water filters from natural dams." According to some historical sources, the Great Pyramid was built over a spring and therefore there is a stream of water beside it. The emblem of the city appears in the colonial codex of "Historia Tolteca Chichimeca". It presents the reeds over an eye of water, and a white ahuejote next to it. Many symbols of water currents also appear in this document, demarcating Cholula as a place where springs and rivers were abundant. Another water reservoir or swamp was located to the east, where the campus of the University of the Americas Puebla (UDLAP) is located today.

Reference: Merlo Juárez, Eduardo. "Cholula, La Roma De Mesoamérica". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 24-30.

Reference: Peterson, David. "The Real Cholula". *Notas Mesoamericanas* 10 (1987): 71-118.

Reference: Pueblos Originarios. "Anales De Cuauhtinchan. Historia Totlteca-chichimeca.". Accessed 2024. <https://pueblosoriginarios.com/meso/valle/tolteca/anales.html>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Religious Specialists

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

—Yes

Type of feature

—Mound

Notes: "Tlachihualtépetl" is a Nahuatl word that means "man-made hill/mountain". After the abandonment of the Great Pyramid as the main ceremonial center of the city in the 6th century, the structure deteriorated until it looked like a small natural elevation after losing its architectural finishes and plants flourished on it. When the Hispanics arrived, it already had that appearance and historical sources represent it as a small hill with a reticulated surface, denoting that its core was made of adobe. Also, it usually appears with a stream of water next to it.

Reference: de Rojas, Gabriel. "Relación De Cholula (1581)". In *Relaciones Geográficas Del Siglo XVI*, edited by René Acuña, Tomo II:121-45. México: UNAM, 1984.

Reference: González-Hermosillo Adam, Francisco, and Luis Reyes García. *El Códice De Cholula: La Exaltación Testimonial De Un Linaje Indio*. México: INAH, CIESAS, 2002.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

—Yes

Notes: The remains of the ancient sacred city of Cholula (Tollan Cholollan Tlachihualtepetl) are located under the urban area of the modern cities of San Pedro Cholula and San Andrés Cholula. After the Spanish conquest in the 16th century, a new European-style settlement was built on top of the pre-Hispanic city. This new city maintained the ancient orientation, which is that of the Great Pyramid, but most of the temples and pre-Hispanic buildings were destroyed. Perhaps due to its large dimensions and the hill-like appearance it had, the mound of the Great Pyramid was preserved and maintained for some time as a local sanctuary dedicated to the rain deities until the construction of the Templo de Nuestra Señora de los Remedios at the end of the 16th century.

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

— Yes

Notes: Today Cholula is part of the archaeological zones that are open to the public in Mexico. An archaeological zone is a place where evidence of activities that have occurred in the past, whether prehistoric, historical or almost contemporary, has been preserved; also, it means that the site has been investigated archaeologically. The Cholula Archaeological Zone comprises an area of more than 125,000 square meters between the limits of San Pedro Cholula and San Andrés Cholula, which includes the mound of the Great Pyramid (excluding the Nuestra Señora de los Remedios Temple), the open area to the south, a section to the northeast, and the museum of the site. This area is under the protection and administration of the Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia (INAH). <https://www.inah.gob.mx/zonas-arqueologicas> https://lugares.inah.gob.mx/es/zonas-arqueologicas/zonas/1776-cholula.html?lugar_id=1776

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

— Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

— No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

— No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

— Yes

↳ A single structure

— No

↳ One single feature

— Mound

Notes: The architectural complex of the Great Pyramid became a mound in the centuries prior to the Spanish Conquest (1519 AD). The first abandonment occurred around the 6th century (by the end of the Classic Period) and during the time of 900-1150 AD (Aquiáhuac Phase) the place was reoccupied. Afterwards the complex ceased to be the political and religious center of the city.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Cueva. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Pueblos Originarios. "Anales De Cuauhtinchan. Historia Totlteca-chichimeca.". Accessed 2024. <https://pueblosoriginarios.com/meso/valle/tolteca/anales.html>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 600 CE

↳ A group of structures:

— Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

— No

Notes: The architectural sequence of the Great Pyramid was first investigated by Ignacio Marquina through the information exposed in the exploration tunnels. This laid the foundation for later studies on the monument like those by Peterson and McCafferty. Recently, the Tetimpa Project investigations managed to detail its architectural designs and date its occupation sequence. Between the years 100 B.C. and 50 AD Cholula was a minor center of the Puebla-Tlaxcala Valley with residential and ceremonial platforms. Around the year 100 AD, the urbanization of the place and the construction of the first monumental buildings began after the eruption of the

Popocatépetl. Between the 1st and 6th centuries, the ceremonial center of the city was located in the place where the Great Pyramid is located today. After certain periods of time the place was renovated and the new constructions covered a large part of the previous ones, creating larger versions of the monument. Now we know that there are at least 8 construction stages. In general, the designs of the precinct since its first monumental version (Edificio de los Chapulines) constituted complex acropolis-type platforms, with various functional spaces located on its different flanks. In addition, other types of constructions such as basements, plazas, palaces and habitational complexes were also attached to it. Between 900 and 1150 AD, spaces in the Great Pyramid were reused (by the Olmeca-Xicalanca), but later it was abandoned; the place became a shrine and elite necropolis during the following centuries.

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio . *Aquitectura Prehispánica. Memorias Del INAH No.1*. México: INAH, 1951.

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio, ed.. *Proyecto Cholula*. Edited by Ignacio Marquina. Serie De Investigaciones No.19. México: INAH, 1970.

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio . "Cholula, Puebla". In *Los Pueblos Y Señoríos Teocráticos: El Periodo De Las Ciudades Urbanas, Primera Parte*, edited by Eduardo Matos, 109-22. México: SEP, INAH, 1975.

Reference: Peterson, David. "The Real Cholula". *Notas Mesoamericanas* 10 (1987): 71-118.

Reference: McCafferty, Geoffrey. "Reinterpreting the Great Pyramid of Cholula". *Ancient Mesoamerica* 7, no. 1 (1996): 1-17.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. *Cholula*. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 0 CE - 600 CE

— No

Notes: The political, ceremonial and administrative center of the city moved northwest of the Great Pyramid between the 11th and 12th centuries, when the first version of the Temple of Quetzalcoatl should have been built at the place that would be the Great Plaza. This happened after a period of economic, political and demographic depression in Cholula between 650 and 900 AD, and around the later conquest of the city by the Tolteca-Chichimeca in the 12th century. The latest version of temple is described in some historical sources as one of the most important temples in the Mesoamerican world and perhaps was the highest building at that time. The temple was part of an enclosure delimited by platforms that included plazas, shrines, residences and other buildings, and was in function when the Hispanics arrived in 1519. It was destroyed over the next decade and the Franciscans built a wooden structure over its ruins in 1529.

Reference: de Rojas, Gabriel. "Relación De Cholula (1581)". In *Relaciones Geográficas Del Siglo XVI*, edited by René Acuña, Tomo II:121-45. México: UNAM, 1984.

Reference: Díaz del Castillo, Bernal. *Historia Verdadera De La Conquista De La Nueva España*. México: Editorial Patria, 1983.

Reference: Motolinía, Fray Toribio de Benavente. *Historia De Los Indios De La Nueva España*. México: Porrúa, 1969.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. *Cholula*. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Lind, Michael, and Catalina Barrientos. "Así Era La Gran Plaza De Tollan-cholollan". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 48-53.

Reference: Pueblos Originarios. "Anales De Cuauhtinchan. Historia Totlteca-chichimeca.". Accessed 2024.
<https://pueblosoriginarios.com/meso/valle/tolteca/anales.html>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1519 CE

l > A group of features:

— Yes

Notes: The settlement of Cholula has a long sequence of pre-Hispanic occupation, but many features have been destroyed because of the growth of the post-Hispanic and modern city. In the outskirts of the monumental area, vestiges from two early villages (900 BC-100 AD) have been discovered; these were small farming hamlets. One was part of a group of scattered households between a system of swamps located on the UDLAP campus and the other was in the northeastern area of the Great Pyramid. Other features from this period have been

archaeologically explored in the area of UDLAP; some are pits that were excavated in the sterile subsoil such as burials, ovens for roasting food or trunk-conical pits for storage which were filled with domestic garbage at its closing; also underneath the second stage of the Great Pyramid some of this kind of pits were identified. Remains of structures with adobe platforms have also been found north of the Great Pyramid dating back to 200 BC to 100 AD, and the Edificio de la Olla, which is an adobe platform (1st century AD) that constitutes the first construction stage of the Great Pyramid. Middens have been also documented (50-450 AD, Classic period) on the UDLAP campus, which are pits for the extraction of construction material from the sterile soil and were later filled with objects and utensils used in important events and/or celebrations. Remains of houses dating from this period (100-650 AD) and indirect evidence of the presence of households have been documented, such as adobe platforms and burials with offerings on the UDLAP campus. Of similar temporality, burials and remains of houses (site R-016), an oven and the patio of a possible palace (on the grounds of the Villas Arqueológicas hotel) have also been investigated by INAH salvage excavations. From the period between 650 AD and 900 AD the evidence of cultural features is scarce. The period from 900 AD onwards (Postclassic) presents a record of burials (bulk and cremated disposed inside vessels), platforms and residential structures that were built on top, to the south and north of Tlachihualtépetl, as well as on the UDLAP campus, where an oven was also discovered. Altars (like small platforms) with funerary offerings have also been found such as the "Altar Mexica", the "Altar Sin Nombre" and another with representations of skulls and long bones on its sides; these date to the later part of the Postclassic period.

Reference: López, Aurelio, and Gabriela Uruñuela. "Capacidad De Almacenamiento En Pozos Troncocónicos De Cholula, Puebla.". In *Memorias Del Simposio Internacional "arqueología De Almacenamiento En Tiempos Prehispánicos Desde El Norte De México Hasta El Altiplano Central*, edited by Véronique Darras, Séverine Bortot, and Dominique Michelet. México: CEMCA, Universidad de San Luis Potosí, Université de Paris 1, 2012.

Reference: Mauricio Gómez, Natalia. *Celebraciones Y Parafernalia Ritual En Cinco Basureros Del Formativo Terminal-clásico Temprano En Cholula*. Cholula: Unpublished master's thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2010.

Reference: Mountjoy, Joseph, and David Peterson. "man and Land at Prehispanic Cholula. *Publications in Anthropology*, No. 4. Nashville: Vanderbilt University, 1973.

Reference: Müller, Florencia. "La Extensión Arqueológica De Cholula a Través Del Tiempo.". *Comunicaciones, Fundación Alemana para la Investigación Científica*, 8 (1973): 19-22.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Romero Butrón, Ashuni, and Carlos Cedillo Ortega. "Excavando En Las Calles De Cholula: El Reto Del Progreso.". *Arqueología Mexicana XX*, no. 115 (2012): 74-75.

Reference: Salomón, Teresa, Elba Domínguez, and Gabriela Uruñuela. "Vasos Y Braseros, Cerámicas Y Rituales Del Clásico En Cholula.". In *Migración, Población, Territorio Y Cultura. Homenaje a Román Piña Chan*, edited by Julieta Aréchiga. México: SMA, IIA, UNAM, 2006.

Reference: Suárez Cruz, Sergio. *Un Entierro Del Clásico Superior En Cholula, Puebla*. Cuaderno De Trabajo, No. 6. México: Centro Regional de Puebla INAH, 1985.

Reference: Suárez Cruz, Sergio. *Últimos Descubrimientos De Entierros Posclásicos En Cholula, Puebla*. Cuaderno De Trabajo, No. 7. México: Centro Regional de Puebla INAH, 1989.

Reference: Suárez Cruz, Sergio, and Silvia Martínez Arriaga. "Breve Historia De La Arqueología De Cholula, Puebla.". *Antropología. Revista Interdisciplinaria Del INAH 78* (2005): 87-94.

Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The Cholula settlement covered 1.5 square kilometers during its earliest stages and probably 8 square kilometers at its greatest extent in the Cholula III phase (350-450 AD). In the Postclassic period (900-1519 AD) it was already considered a sacred city, but it was also an autonomous political entity that controlled the territory on its periphery and it encompassed other communities in the central area of the Alto Atoyac Valley. Towards the end of the Postclassic period, the entity was bordered to the north by Tlaxcallan, to the east by Cuauhtinchan, to the south by Totomiuacan and to the west by Huexotzinco. By the 16th century, the kingdom of Cholula was surrounded by the kingdoms of Tlaxcala to the north, Tepeaca to the east, Huaquechula to the south, and Huejotzingo to the west. The kingdom of Cholula covered around 800 square kilometers and included more than 50 subjected towns.

Reference: González-Hermosillo Adam, Francisco. *Cholollan Ypan Tlalixtli. Cholula Sobre El Ombligo De La Tierra: El Esplendor Prehispánico De Los Tolteca-chololteca*. México:

CONACULTA, INAH, Ayuntamiento de San Pedro Cholula, 2013.

Reference: González-Hermosillo Adam, Francisco. "San Andrés Cholula En La Época Colonial: Una Crónica De Acontecimientos". In *300 Años, República De Indios, 16 De Octubre 1714*. Cholula: Ayuntamiento de San Andrés Cholula, 2014.

Reference: Lind, Michael. "La Gran Cuadra De La Ciudad: El Gobierno Prehispánico De Cholula". *Arqueología* 39 (2008): 65-76.

Reference: Müller, Florencia. "La Extensión Arqueológica De Cholula a Través Del Tiempo.". *Comunicaciones, Fundación Alemana para la Investigación Científica*, 8 (1973): 19-22.

What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 BCE - 1519 CE

Worship:

– Communal

Notes: Temple of Quetzalcoatl Historical sources indicate that the reliquary with the cremated remains of Quetzalcoatl was kept in this temple and the idol of Quetzalcoatl was located in a chamber on top of a sumptuously decorated altar. Veneration rituals were performed, including sacrifices and self-sacrifice of priests; also offerings and presents were given by local religious officials, but also by dignitaries or merchants who came from foreign regions.

Reference: López de Gómara, Francisco. *Historia De La Conquista De México*. Estudio preliminar de Juan Miralles Ostos. México: Porrúa, 1988.

Reference: Motolinía, Fray Toribio de Benavente. *Historia De Los Indios De La Nueva España*. México: Porrúa, 1969.

Reference: Muñoz Camargo, Diego. *Descripción De La Ciudad Y Provincia De Tlaxcala*. Edited by René Acuña. *Relaciones Geográficas Del Siglo XVI: Tlaxcala, T.I*. México: UNAM, 1984.

Reference: Hermann Lejarazu, Manuel A. . "Códice Nuttall. Lado 1: La Vida De 8 Venado.". *Arqueología Mexicana Edición Especial*, no. 23 (2007).

Reference: Noticonquista. "Quetzalcoatl Negro". Accessed 2024. <https://www.noticonquista.unam.mx/amoxtli/1247/1247>.

Reference: The British Museum. "The Tonindeye Codex". Accessed 2024. https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/E_Am1902-0308-1.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

– Communal

Notes: Great Pyramid of Cholula According to recent interpretations (Tetimpa Project) on the Edificio de los Chapulines (first monumental building in the construction sequence of the Great Pyramid), it is likely that this structure was built as a product of the social integration process after the catastrophe caused by the eruption of the Popocatepetl volcano. This event preceded the urban development of Cholula in the 1st century AD. The symbolism and the labor invested in its construction create the social ties necessary to build a new society made by foreign communities. Thus, this acropolis provided spaces for the worship and veneration of their ancestors. For the following construction stages, the architecture shows significant changes that perhaps denotes different kinds of cults or political orientations. Perhaps the large and elevated western esplanade of the Edificio de los Tableros suggests to a new cult to the volcanoes on the western horizon, and the continuous staircases of the Stepped Buildings proclaim discourses of accessibility to the divine. In any case, the acropolis at its different stages evoked the concept of the sacred mountain (even after its abandonment), which was a fundamental concept in the Mesoamerican ideology, being a kind of axis mundi where the horizontal and vertical realms converged. Other authors such as McCafferty have proposed that the Great Pyramid was the "mountain of sustenance", given that it was associated with terrestrial and celestial waters. By connecting the Underworld with the Upperworld, it linked divine dualities. In later times, the mound of the Great Pyramid or Tlachihualtepetl housed a sanctuary dedicated to the rain deities. Gabriel de Rojas wrote in 1581 that there was an idol at its summit called "chiconahuh quiahuitl" (9 rain) to which the local population dedicated sacrifices and prayers meant to ask for rain.

Reference: de Rojas, Gabriel. "Relación De Cholula (1581)". In *Relaciones Geográficas Del Siglo XVI*, edited by René Acuña, Tomo II:121-45. México: UNAM, 1984.

Reference: Uruñuela, Gabriela, Patricia Plunket, and María Amparo Robles. "Cholula: Art and Architecture of an Archetypal City.". In *The Art of Urbanism: How Mesoamerican Kingdoms Represented Themselves in Architecture and Imagery.*, edited by William L. Fash and Leonardo López Luján, 135-71. Washington DC: Dumbarton Oaks, 2009.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. *Motivación Y Cambio Culturales: Los Orígenes De La Gran Pirámide De Cholula.* Cholula: Unpublished bachelor thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2007.

Reference: McCafferty, Geoffrey. "Mountain of Heaven, Mountain of Earth: The Great Pyramid of Cholula as Sacred Landscape". In *Landscape and Power in Mesoamerica*, edited by Rex Koontz, Kathryn Reese Taylor, and Annabeth Headrick, 279-316. Boulder: Westview Press, 2001.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. *Cholula.* México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 1519 CE

— Political

Notes: Like most Mesoamerican ceremonial centers, the central precinct of Cholula (the acropolis of the Great Pyramid and later the Great Plaza) always concentrated spaces with both religious and political functions. For the Classic structures, it is difficult to differentiate which spaces fulfilled exclusively political or religious functions, since we should remember that Mesoamerican state structures were always linked to religious ones. In the acropolis of the Great Pyramid, there are spaces that during the Classic period must have fulfilled both functions. Palaces and other adjoining high-status spaces must have included places to carry out activities related to the administration and coordination of the government. For example, the plazas (above or around the acropolis) were meeting places for specific groups or the community in general (such as the Patio de los Altares), whether for political propaganda or religious ceremonies. During the Postclassic period, the plan of the Great Plaza of Tollan Cholollan in the codex *Historia Tolteca Chichimeca* shows how both temples and altars were located there, as well as residences of priests, noble lords and warriors, and "offices" where priests and nobles fulfilled their duties and tasks derived from their rank. An example is the "casilla especial", where the two high priests of Cholula (Tlalchiach and Aquiach) confirmed foreign rulers in their position by piercing their nose, lobes or lower lip to place a jewel that was the insignia of their royalty. The Xuicalli, to the west of the Great Plaza, was the room where the Council of the six noble lords met.

Reference: Las Casas, Fray Bartolomé. *Los Indios De México Y Nueva España: Antología.* Edited by Edmundo O'Gorman and Jorge A. Manrique. 2nd edition. México: Porrúa, 1971.

Reference: Lind, Michael. "La Gran Cuadra De La Ciudad: El Gobierno Prehispánico De Cholula". *Arqueología* 39 (2008): 65-76.

Reference: Lind, Michael, and Catalina Barrientos. "Así Era La Gran Plaza De Tollan-cholollan". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 48-53.

Reference: Hermann Lejarazu, Manuel A. "Códice Nuttall. Lado 1: La Vida De 8 Venado.". *Arqueología Mexicana Edición Especial*, no. 23 (2007).

Reference: Pueblos Originarios. "Anales De Cuauhtinchan. Historia Totlteca-chichimeca.". Accessed 2024. <https://pueblosoriginarios.com/meso/valle/tolteca/anales.html>.

Reference: The British Museum. "The Tonindeye Codex". Accessed 2024. https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/E_Am1902-0308-1.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

— Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

— Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

— Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

— Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

— Collapsed

Notes: The Great Pyramid Acropolis After the abandonment of the acropolis (Great Pyramid) towards the end of the Classic period, the structures and their complexes were eroded into ruins. Towards the 10th century, the place was re-occupied and some construction projects took place there. In the 12th century it was definitively abandoned as the seat of the political authority. (See Chronology of Cholula by Plunket y Uruñuela 2018:Cuadro1.1).

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 1200 CE

— Burned

Notes: The Temple of Quetzalcoatl In October 1519, the Spanish and their Tlaxcalan allies surprisingly attacked the Cholultecas. A great massacre occurred and many houses and temples were burned, including, apparently, the Temple of Quetzalcoatl. In the following decade it would be completely destroyed to build the Franciscan convent complex of San Gabriel.

Reference: Torquemada, Fray Juan de . Monarquía Indiana. México: UNAM, 1975.

Reference: Proyecto Lienzo de Tlaxcala. "Lámina 9: Chololla". Reconstrucción Histórica Digital del Lienzo de Tlaxcala. Accessed 2024. <https://lienzodetlaxcala.unam.mx/lamina-9/>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1519 CE - 1529 CE

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

—For religious reasons

—For political reasons

—As the result of war

Notes: The central precinct of the Great Plaza and the city The Temple of Quetzalcoatl along with the structures of the Great Plaza and the temples of the city were deliberately destroyed by the Hispanics to build a new European-style city on its ruins. This was also intended to erase all vestiges of local cults and pre-Hispanic religion in order to teach and impose the new Catholic religion on the people. However, the orientation of the blocks maintained that of the ancient city.

Reference: Merlo Juárez, Eduardo. "Cholula, La Roma De Mesoamérica". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 24–30.

Reference: de Rojas, Gabriel. "Relación De Cholula (1581)". In *Relaciones Geográficas Del Siglo XVI*, edited by René Acuña, Tomo II:121–45. México: UNAM, 1984.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1519 CE - 1529 CE

—For political reasons

Notes: Patio de los Altares At the end of the 6th century, the monuments known as Altar 1, Altar 2 and Altar 3 in the main southern plaza of (Patio de los Altares) the Great Pyramid acropolis were intentionally destroyed. Apparently these are two altar-throne complexes (teoicpallin = sacred seat) where the rulers and/or priests of the city performed public ceremonies. Its destruction suggests socio-economic problems or the confrontation of political factions.

Reference: Peterson, David. "The Real Cholula". *Notas Mesoamericanas* 10 (1987): 71–118.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia. "El Patio De Los Altares En La Gran Pirámide De Cholula: La Violenta Destrucción De Los Iconos". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 42–47.

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio, ed. Proyecto Cholula. Edited by Ignacio Marquina. Serie De Investigaciones No.19. México: INAH, 1970.

Reference: Testard, Juliette. "Secuencias Performativas Y Destrucción Ritual De Esculturas Enmesoamérica. Algunas Hipótesis Desde Cacaxtla, Xochicalco Y Cholula (México) Durante El Epiclásico (600a 900 D. C.)". *Americae* 4 (2019): 71–90. <https://hal.science/hal-02468168>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 BCE - 650 CE

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: Historical events

Notes: The Great Pyramid or Tlachihualtepetl: abandonment-political reasons, and posterior erosion The Temple of Quetzalcoatl: battle, fire, demolition

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Notes: Temple of Quetzalcoatl The Temple of Quetzalcoatl, despite confusing and contradictory information about its history, may also have been remodeled periodically throughout the centuries while it functioned as the main temple of the sacred city (12th to 16th centuries). This practice was very common in many similar Mesoamerican monuments such as the acropolis of the Great Pyramid of Cholula, or the Templo Mayor of Tenochtitlán.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1519 CE

– Periodically

Notes: The acropolis of the Great Pyramid The sequence of construction stages of the Great Pyramid shows that during the Classic period the central precinct was remodeled and enlarged periodically as part of political projects of the elites that governed the city. Through the architecture they transmitted specific messages to the community.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Cueva. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 900 CE

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: Here we could consider the reconstruction works carried out in the Archaeological Zone, towards the end of the investigations of the Proyecto Cholula, which accomplished several consolidation and reconstruction works such as the wide southern staircase in the Patio de los Altares and the so-called Toltec platform on its western façade.

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio, ed.. Proyecto Cholula. Edited by Ignacio Marquina. Serie De Investigaciones No.19. México: INAH, 1970.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1967 CE - 1971 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Deities and numens

Notes: The feathered serpent must have been a worshiped supernatural being since the beginnings of the city of Cholula. Representations of this being since the early stages of the acropolis of the Great Pyramid have been identified in the reliefs of the Platform of the Chapulincitos on the Edificio de los Chapulines (1st century). Also the Jaguar Platform (contemporary to the former) has a mural where there are jaguars and feathered snakes in what appears to be an epic fight. Another feathered serpents, that are intertwined, are sculpted on the edges of Altar 2 in the Patio de los Altares (6th century). Quetzalcoatl was the tutelary deity of the sacred city of Cholula during the Postclassic, and the temple dedicated to him is well identified in the historical sources. However, the archaeological record presents other evidence about the worship of other supernatural beings or deities such as: Xochipilli (Mexica Altar); Xipe Tótec, Macuilxóchitl and rain deities (Altar Sin Nombre); the feathered serpent (Altar 2); Xiuhcóatl (sculpture found among the earth fillings above the Patio of the Altares); the deity of rain and lightning (in association to the Chacmool found south of the Great Pyramid).

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. Motivación Y Cambio Culturales: Los Orígenes De La Gran Pirámide De Cholula.. Cholula: Unpublished bachelor thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2007.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo, and María Teresa Salomón Salazar. "Gran Pirámide De Cholula, Diagnóstico Sector Sureste, Arqueología.". Proyecto De Rehabilitación De La Escalinata Del Pocito De La Zona Arqueológica De Cholula, 2021.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 600 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

— Yes

Notes: Quetzalcoatl derives from Nahuatl terms from the "emerald plumed serpent". This avian serpent appear during the earliest times in Mesoamerica among the Olmec culture. By the transition from the Classic to the Postclassic this being became a more complex figure and it is considered a god-man. One of his main denominations is as the god of the wind that gives life (this Quetzalcoatl usually wears a red mask with a duck-like beak), the wind that brings the clouds (Ehécatl), but he can be also creator and orderer of the universe by other mythic narratives. On the other hand, Quetzalcóatl as Ce Acatl Topiltzin has the connotation of a priest and/or hero, becoming a central historical figure for the Central Mexican Highlands. Apparently his relics were kept inside the main temple of the city of Cholula. In this general way, Quetzalcoatl constitutes an ideological complex that links myth with history.

Reference: López Austin, Alfredo. *Hombre-dios: Religión Y Política En El Mundo Náhuatl*. 2nd ed. México: UNAM, 2022.

Reference: Miller, Mary, and Karl Taube. *Al Illustrated Dictionary of the Gods and Symbols of Ancient Mexico and the Maya*. Singapore: Thames and Hudson, 1993.

Reference: Pueblos Originarios. "Código Florentino". Accessed 2024. <https://pueblosoriginarios.com/meso/valle/azteca/codices/florentino/florentino.html>.

Reference: Pueblos Originarios. "Manuscrito Tovar. Código Ramírez.". Accessed 2024. <https://pueblosoriginarios.com/textos/tovar/tovar.html>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 650 CE - 1519 CE

Is it a cenotaph:

— No

Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

— Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

— Yes

Is it a cenotaph:

— No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

— Yes

Notes: The Edificio de los Chapulines was built at the end of the 1st century, after the Popocatepetl eruption. It measures 108 meters east-west by 130m north-south and is oriented 24° east of true north. Its total height, including the upper enclosure that crowns the platform (a raised quadrangle), is 18.5 meters, but taking into account the weight of the structures that support it on top, it is likely that it was originally one meter higher. It is a 7-level platform, with contours that are not always symmetrical, and the two upper bodies are decorated with tableros and mural paintings on its north façade. Its design is similar to an acropolis, with access from its four sides, but the north and west facades should be the main ones; there are also two rooms and several plazas at different levels that must have been scenery for the performance of diverse ceremonies. The Edificio de los Chapulines was probably dedicated to the ancestors of a new community settled after surviving the catastrophic volcanic eruption of the 1st century. The architectural and pictorial program shows that the building became the place where all the ancestors of this people congregated.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. Motivación Y Cambio Culturales: Los Orígenes De La Gran Pirámide De Cholula.. Cholula: Unpublished bachelor thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2007.

Reference: Uruñuela, Gabriela, Patricia Plunket, and María Amparo Robles. "Cholula: Art and Architecture of an Archetypal City.". In *The Art of Urbanism: How Mesoamerican Kingdoms Represented Themselves in Architecture and Imagery.*, edited by William L. Fash and Leonardo López Luján, 135-71. Washington DC: Dumbarton Oaks, 2009.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 BCE - 150 CE

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

— Yes

↳ Specify

— Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

Notes: The architectural and pictorial program visible in the structures of the southern section of the acropolis integrate symbolic compositions on the talud-tablero elements, such as that of the alt-tepetl (water-mountain, concept of city-state), the sacred mountain-cave (axis-mundi), and other emblems of authority (petate/mat weaving). All of them in some way reflect the proclamation of Cholula as the axis mundi and sacred city. That means that Cholula was recognized as a formal political entity at least since around the year 300 AD.

Reference: McCafferty, Geoffrey. "Mountain of Heaven, Mountain of Earth: The Great Pyramid of Cholula as Sacred Landscape". In *Landscape and Power in Mesoamerica*, edited by Rex Koontz, Kathryn Reese Taylor, and Annabeth Headrick, 279-316. Boulder: Westview Press, 2001.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia. "El Patio De Los Altares En La Gran Pirámide De Cholula: La Violenta Destrucción De Los Iconos". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 42-47.

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio, ed.. *Proyecto Cholula*. Edited by Ignacio Marquina. Serie De Investigaciones No.19. México: INAH, 1970.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1 BCE - 1519 CE

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

— Yes

↳ Groups:

— Specialized labourers/craftspeople

— Other [specify]: Commoners

Notes: Most of the labor force employed for the construction of the Great Pyramid should have been from commoners. Probably, one individual from each family group from the community

would have been involved in those construction projects, when agricultural activities were on pause. It is very likely that there were certain specialists such as stonemasons, supervisors, crew leaders, painters and perhaps architects. However, the study on the construction process of the Edificio de los Chapulines showed that 99.9% of the construction labor appears to have been carried out by non-specialized personnel. Because the construction systems do not seem to have varied very much between the earliest and latest stages (with the exception of the Edificio Escalonado 1) of the acropolis, we can assume that the proportion was similar in the overall construction sequence.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. *Construyendo La Gran Pirámide De Cholula: Energía Y Complejidad Social*. Cholula: Unpublished master's thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2012.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 600 CE

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: Natural events: Volcanic eruption of the Popocatepetl

Notes: The eruption of Popocatepetl, to the west of the Puebla-Tlaxcala Valley, detonated and catalyzed socio-economic processes in the first century that led to the emergence of Cholula as the most important center of the valley during the Classic. After this event, the first monumental version of the Great Pyramid was built: the Edificio de los Chapulines. A second eruption of the same volcano, which took place in the 7th century, is associated with an economic, political and demographic depression in Cholula. Later, the Olmeca-Xicalanca arrived in the city. By the 12th century, after the Toltec-Chichimec conquered the place, the political center of the city moved to the northwest of the former acropolis and the new Temple of Quetzalcoatl was built.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Plunket, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela. "Preclassic Household Patterns Preserved Under Volcanic Ash at Tetimpa, Puebla, Mexico". *Latin American Antiquity* 9, no. 4 (December 1998). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3537029>.

Reference: Uruñuela, Gabriela, Patricia Plunket, and María Amparo Robles. "Cholula: Art and Architecture of an Archetypal City". In *The Art of Urbanism: How Mesoamerican Kingdoms Represented Themselves in Architecture and Imagery*, edited by William L. Fash and Leonardo López Luján, 135-71. Washington DC: Dumbarton Oaks, 2009.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 75 CE - 100 CE

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: In general, the Mesoamerican platforms emulated the sacred mountain. Through ritual practices on them, as it has been noted for the acropolis of the Great Pyramid, the divine was propitiated in order to satisfy the material and ideological human needs.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 BCE - 1519 CE

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Edificio de los Tableros Lisos The Edificio de los Tableros Lisos (3rd construction stage of the Great Pyramid), unlike the previous version of the Edificio de los Chapulines, presents a wide terrace extended to the west. It was built in the second half of the 3rd century and its design and shape were inferred by the record of its features cut by the tunnels. It had seven levels and measured 145m north-south by 178m east-west. The floors of the 5 lower levels are "T" shaped, perhaps evoking the concept of the cave or the mountain. The greatest volumetric weight is thus towards the west, the direction where the volcanoes rise. It must have formed a large plaza (100m north-south by 80m east-west) in conjunction with another big structure to the west (now the mound of Cerro de la Cruz). This indicates that the ceremonial center was growing towards that direction and possibly the ceremonial activity of this time was linked to the volcanoes.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Uruñuela, Gabriela, Patricia Plunket, and María Amparo Robles. "Cholula: Art and Architecture of an Archetypal City.". In *The Art of Urbanism: How Mesoamerican Kingdoms Represented Themselves in Architecture and Imagery.*, edited by William L. Fash and Leonardo López Luján, 135-71. Washington DC: Dumbarton Oaks, 2009.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. *Motivación Y Cambio Culturales: Los Orígenes De La Gran Pirámide De Cholula.* Cholula: Unpublished bachelor thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2007.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 150 BCE - 200 CE

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: Recent investigations on the construction stages that formed the acropolis of the Great Pyramid shows that the renovations of each new stage often left sections of previous buildings visible. In addition, there were other complexes of structures that were attached to its flanks, as can be seen in the southern sector. In the case of the Edificio de los Tableros Lisos, a large part of the Upper North Plaza, where the Chapulincitos platform is located, and the northeast sector of the Edificio de los Chapulines, were exposed and integrated into its design. Another case is the Jaguar Platform (contemporary with the Chapulines) in the south-eastern corner of the Great Pyramid, which was not covered by the Edificio Escalonado 1 and 2. The Edificio Escalonado 2 left the terraces to the east of the previous stage visible. In the southern sector, a great architectural complexity is observed, since the renovation projects also meant the destruction of important portions of structures in order to create new facades, different platforms, or other architectural features, which were attached to each other or even to the central module of the acropolis.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Uruñuela, Gabriela, Patricia Plunket, and María Amparo Robles. "Cholula: Art and Architecture of an Archetypal City.". In *The Art of Urbanism: How Mesoamerican Kingdoms Represented Themselves in Architecture and Imagery.*, edited by William L. Fash and Leonardo López Luján, 135-71. Washington DC: Dumbarton Oaks, 2009.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. *Motivación Y Cambio Culturales: Los Orígenes De La Gran Pirámide De Cholula.* Cholula: Unpublished bachelor thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2007.

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio, ed.. *Proyecto Cholula.* Edited by Ignacio Marquina. Serie De Investigaciones No.19. México: INAH, 1970.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo, and María Teresa Salomón Salazar. "Gran Pirámide De Cholula, Diagnóstico Sector Sureste, Arqueología.". Proyecto De Rehabilitación De La Escalinata Del Pocito De La Zona Arqueológica De Cholula, 2021.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 BCE - 700 CE

→ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The pattern of architectural extensions documented in the Great Pyramid and its surroundings indicates that the acropolis of the Great Pyramid, through its different periods, occupied a central place in the physical and ritual geography of the city. There were other important buildings but they are smaller and less complex, such as the Templo Rojo to the northwest, the complex of palaces and residences to the south, and relevant platforms to the west (Cerro de la Cruz and Cerro Acozac). However, none of these structures achieved preeminence over the central acropolis.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 1519 CE

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The Edificio de los Chapulines is the 1st monumental building. From that time on (1st century AD) there were several monuments that were periodically built, rebuilt and renovated over and around the acropolis.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 1519 CE

→ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

→ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 160000

Notes: Approximate footprint areas (square meters) of the different stages of the acropolis of the Great Pyramid (architectural sequence from Plunket and Uruñuela 2018): 14,000 Edificio de los Chapulines (Robles 2007) 25,000 Edificio de los Tableros Lisos (Robles 2007) 58,200 Edificio Escalonado 1 (Plunket y Uruñuela 2018) 65,500 Edificio Escalonado 2 (Plunket y Uruñuela 2018) 68,800 (?) Edificio 6 (estimated from plan in Marquina 1970) 92,000 (?) Edificio 7 (estimated from plan in Marquina 1970) 160,000 Edificio 8 (Marquina 1951).

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio. *Aquitectura Prehispánica. Memorias Del INAH No.1. México: INAH, 1951.*

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. *Motivación Y Cambio Culturales: Los Orígenes De La Gran Pirámide De Cholula.. Cholula: Unpublished bachelor thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2007.*

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio, ed.. *Proyecto Cholula. Edited by Ignacio Marquina. Serie De Investigaciones No.19. México: INAH, 1970.*

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 600 CE

→ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 45

Notes: This is an estimation for the Templo de Quetzalcoatl made by Salomón and Torres (2021). Some historical sources describe aspects of the temple, but there is not enough information to establish a safe figure. The first conquerors commented that to go up to the

temple of Quetzalcóatl there were between 100 and 120 steps; they also wrote that it was higher than the Templo Mayor of Tenochtitlán.

Reference: Salomón Salazar, María Teresa, and Alicia Torres Porras. "Guión Museológico Y Museográfico De La Exposición"la Gran Cholula De Los Tolteca-chichimecas"", 2021.

Reference: Díaz del Castillo, Bernal. Historia Verdadera De La Conquista De La Nueva España. México: Editorial Patria, 1983.

Reference: López de Gómara, Francisco. Historia De La Conquista De México. Estudio preliminar de Juan Miralles Ostos.. México: Porrúa, 1988.

Reference: Cervantes de Salazar, Francisco . "Crónica De La Nueva España, Edición De Manuel Magallón.", 1971. <https://www.cervantesvirtual.com/obra/cronica-de-la-nueva-espana--0/>.

— Height, meters: 60

Notes: Estimated heights (meters) of the different stages of the acropolis of the Great Pyramid (architectural sequence from Plunket and Uruñuela 2018): 18.5 Edificio de los Chapulines (Robles 2007) 20 Edificio de los Tableros Lisos (Plunket y Uruñuela 2018; Robles 2007) 34.5 Edificio Escalonado 1 (Plunket y Uruñuela 2018) 34.5 Edificio Escalonado 2 (Plunket y Uruñuela 2018) 44.5 Edificio 6 (estimated from plan in Marquina 1970) 53.4 Edificio 7 (estimated from plan in Marquina 1970) 61.7 Edificio 8 (estimated from plan in Marquina 1970)

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio, ed.. Proyecto Cholula. Edited by Ignacio Marquina. Serie De Investigaciones No.19. México: INAH, 1970.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. Motivación Y Cambio Culturales: Los Orígenes De La Gran Pirámide De Cholula.. Cholula: Unpublished bachelor thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2007.

Size of average monument, square meters:

— Field doesn't know

Height of average monument, meters:

— Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

— Yes

Notes: Acropolis of the Great Pyramid Seven of the eight stages in the architectural sequence of the Great Pyramid employed similar construction systems, using earthen materials in an estimated proportion of 88.5% (reference study: Edificio de los Chapulines). All these materials were found in the immediate locality. With the exception of the Edificio Escalonado 1, the basic technique was to create a core of "cajones" (cube-shaped volume) made of adobe and mortar walls. Then it was covered with a flattened layer of clay on which limestone slabs were placed; that surface were finally covered by a concrete-type mixture based on gravels, clay, ground limestone and eventually some lime. Staircases and tableros required a greater proportion of stone blocks.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. Construyendo La Gran Pirámide De Cholula: Energía Y Complejidad Social. Cholula: Unpublished master's thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2012.

Reference: Robles, María Amparo, Gabriela Uruñuela, and Patricia Plunket. "Ingeniería En Tierra E Inversión Energética En La Primera Versión Monumental De La Gran Pirámide De Cholula.". In *Arquitectura Mesoamericana De Tierra*, Volumen 1, edited by Annik Daneels, 69-120. México: UNAM, 2020.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 600 CE

Earth

— Yes

Is this material sourced locally:

— Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are no environmental reconstructions for the pre-Hispanic era of Cholula. Because of that, we consider that 25 kilometers was a feasible distance to obtain wood from the slopes of the Popocatepetl and Iztaccihuatl, such as the pine beam and pillars from the structure of the galleries in the Edificio de los Chapulines.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. Construyendo La Gran Pirámide De Cholula: Energía Y Complejidad Social. Cholula: Unpublished master's thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2012.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. Motivación Y Cambio Culturales: Los Orígenes De La Gran Pirámide De Cholula.. Cholula: Unpublished bachelor thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2007.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 BCE - 1519 CE

↳ Grass
– Yes

Notes: Grass could have been employed in the production of adobes. Another documented use of grass is in the interior plastering of the room on the Plataforma de La Conejera, which is

located at a great depth in the northeastern corner of the Great Pyramid and dates from the Late Formative.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Cueva. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Noguera, Eduardo. "Un Edificio Preclásico En Cholula." In Estudios Antropológicos Publicados En Homenaje Al Doctor Manuel Gamio. México: UNAM and SMA, 1956.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 BCE - 1519 CE

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

— Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

— No

↳ Stone

— Yes

Notes: Limestone was the type of stone used in the greatest proportion for the construction of the substructures of the Great Pyramid, and to a lesser extent other types like rhyolite. About 0.4% of the volume of the Edificio de los Chapulines (ECh) is limestone. This proportion is likely to be similar for the third, and fifth to the eighth stages. Only the fourth, the Edificio Escalonado 1, employed a different system which consisted in a core of large limestone blocks amalgamated with a clay mortar. The ECh study on the probable sources of limestone for Cholula shows that they must have been extracted about 9 kilometers to the east, where the city of Puebla is located today.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Cueva. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. Motivación Y Cambio Culturales: Los Orígenes De La Gran Pirámide De Cholula. Cholula: Unpublished bachelor thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2007.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. Construyendo La Gran Pirámide De Cholula: Energía Y Complejidad Social. Cholula: Unpublished master's thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2012.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 BCE - 250 CE

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

— No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

— Yes

↳ Other

—Other [specify]: Lime

Notes: Some portion of lime may have been used in the mixture of plaster.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

—Yes [specify]: Adobe, clay and gravels plaster

Notes: The raw materials used in the construction of the substructures of the Great Pyramid must be processed in order to be used in the construction of the building: adobe, mortar, stone slabs and blocks, gravels plaster, paint. According to the energetic study of the Edificio de los Chapulines, although we know that the manufacturing tasks were not the most expensive, they are essential.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. Construyendo La Gran Pirámide De Cholula: Energía Y Complejidad Social. Cholula: Unpublished master's thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2012.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Actually, there is virtually no evidence of interior decoration, because the temples on the platforms have not been preserved or explored.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If any decoration of this type existed, no evidence has yet been found or it has not been preserved.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Templo de Quetzalcoatl Historical sources indicate that in the chamber of the Temple of Quetzalcoatl there was the idol of the god on an altar; it was luxuriously decorated with gold, silver, jewels, feathers, precious blankets. It also wore a bird mouth-mask, a shield, and a knife.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Durán, Diego. Ritos Y Fiestas De Los Antiguos Mexicanos.. México: Editorial Innovación, 1980.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There are representations of the feathered serpent possibly from the stage of the Edificio de los Chapulines (on the Plataforma de los Chapulincitos) and later on the edges of Altar 2 of the Patio de los Altares, where a sculpture of the "fire serpent" also appeared (Xihcoatl).

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The most relevant human figures are those that appear in the Mural de los Bebedores, which decorates the exterior façade of a palace dating from the 3rd century and corresponds to the first stages of the Patio de los Altares. On the other hand, the fleshless skulls of the Mural de los Chapulines, which decorate the panels of the northern façade of the second construction stage of the Great Pyramid (Edificio de los Chapulines), could be considered a type of human depiction.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Uruñuela y Ladrón de Guevara, Gabriela, and Patricia Plunket Nagoda. "El Mural De Los Bebedores De Cholula: Ceremonias De Embriaguez.". Arqueología

Are there animals depicted:

— Yes

Notes: Animals depicted in the Great Pyramid are: a possible arthropod (posterior part of its body) in the Mural de los Chapulines, a jaguar with two snakes on the Mural del Jaguar (Plataforma del Jaguar), a monkey in the Mural de los Bebedores and starfish on the murals decorating the tableros, both associated with different stages of the Edificio 3 which is located on the western margin of the Patio de los Altares.

Reference: Uruñuela y Ladrón de Guevara, Gabriela, and Patricia Plunket Nagoda. "El Mural De Los Bebedores De Cholula: Ceremonias De Embriaguez." *Arqueología Mexicana* XIX, no. 114 (2012): 40-43.

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio, ed.. *Proyecto Cholula*. Edited by Ignacio Marquina. Serie De Investigaciones No.19. México: INAH, 1970.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. *Cholula*. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 BCE - 600 CE

Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

— Yes

Notes: Some individuals in the Mural de los Bebedores have animal characteristics such as monkey and bird. However, these may constitute representations of masks worn by the characters depicted there. Some images can be seen here:

<https://arqueologiamexicana.mx/mexico-antiguo/el-mural-de-los-bebedores-de-cholula-ceremonias-de-embriaguez> <https://arqueologiamexicana.mx/mexico-antiguo/el-mural-de-los-bebedores-de-cholula-puebla> <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7u4OEekioCY>

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 300 CE

Is the decoration non-figural:

— Yes

Notes: The design of the stepped slopes of the Edificio Escalado 1 and 2 could be considered an example of non-figurative decoration. This constitutes an unprecedented design for Mesoamerica and it gives the impression of immense stairs that, at least in appearance, would have allowed massive access. This has been interpreted as a continuity in the message of inclusion of the acropolis-like design of the substructures, due to the diversity of spaces (squares and terraces) for carrying out cult activities. The innovative appearance of the Edificio Escalado 1 (and 2) may be the reason why the Mixtecs designate Cholula as "The Place of the Stairs" in later times.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. *Cholula*. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 300 CE

Is it geometric/abstract

— Yes

Notes: The panels of Edificio 3, in the southern section of the Great Pyramid, exhibit extensive decoration of diagonal stripes in red, yellow, orange, white and green. This bands-pattern is often used to designate stone or earth objects (mountains, for example) as in the Mixtec Tonindeye (Zouche-Nuttall) codex.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia. "El Patio De Los Altares En La Gran Pirámide De Cholula: La Violenta Destrucción De Los Iconos". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 42-47.

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio, ed.. *Proyecto Cholula*. Edited by Ignacio Marquina. Serie De Investigaciones No.19. México: INAH, 1970.

Reference: The British Museum. "The Tonindeye Codex". Accessed 2024. https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/E_Am1902-0308-1.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 600 CE

↳ Floral motifs

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Squares

Notes: The tableros of a substructure in the northeastern corner of the Great Pyramid has black squares as decoration. Its architectural association is not well understood because this sector is very complex and no detailed mapping and absolute dating have been done yet.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 BCE - 600 CE

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

Notes: Originally it does not seem that the general decoration of the monuments and buildings was hidden, although access to the temples and palaces was probably restricted to specific religious or political groups. However, these same decorative elements were hidden from view when superimposed structures were built to renovate or expand the buildings in later stages.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 BCE - 1200 CE

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

Notes: Archaeological explorations have allowed the discovery and display of important sections of the decorated elements on the monuments and different substructures of the Great Pyramid of Cholula.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 600 CE

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: The "idol" of the god Quetzalcoatl that historical sources describe as being inside the chamber of the Temple of Quetzalcoatl could be considered the most important cult statue in the history of the Postclassic period in the City of Cholula. According to Durán, the figure was made of wood, the body was that of a man, the face of a bird with a red beak (with a crest and a row of teeth), a painted paper miter, gold earrings and other jewelry, some strips that hung on the back like fringes, colorful feather blankets, gold socks and sandals; in his right hand he had a very sumptuous type of ax and in his left a shield. Regarding previous times there is still no evidence of something similar.

Reference: Durán, Diego. *Ritos Y Fiestas De Los Antiguos Mexicanos*. México: Editorial Innovación, 1980.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The statue of Xiuhcoatl is located in Museo Regional de Cholula and represents a supernatural being, apparently the fire serpent or some supernatural reptile. The aforementioned idol of Quetzalcoatl would be a statue of the god Quetzalcoatl. As

described in historical sources, his attributes and clothing indicates that the depiction corresponded to his dimension as to the wind god Ehécatl.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

Statues of humans:

— Yes

Notes: Monumental sculpture in Cholula is quite scarce. There is a humanoid head with rather schematic features (approximately 1 meter high), currently located in the Patio de los Altares towards the northeast corner. It was probably found in the fills above the patio. Another anthropomorphic sculpture (1.36 m high) was discovered under a floor of a Classic structure; its head and arms were missing, the torso was male with cavities in the armpits (it probably had mobile limbs), it wore a loincloth, a skirt, and ornaments on the knees.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 BCE - 600 CE

Other [Specify]

— Other [specify]: Chacmool and even stele

Notes: There are two other important pieces to mention. The first is Chacmool, which does not fall into any of the previous categories; this piece dates from the Late Postclassic period (1350-1550) and was found south of the Great Pyramid. There is only one example from Cholula, so its specific meaning is unclear, but it corresponds well with the association with rain deities, perhaps symbolically as a ritual bearer or messenger. The other piece is an even stele with a perforation, it was found on the west side of the Great Pyramid in front of Building F. It is currently visible in the archaeological zone.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: López Austin, Alfredo, and Leonardo López Luján. "El Chacmool Mexica". *Caravelle. Cahiers Du Monde Hispanique Et Luso-brésilien* 76, no. 1 (2001): 59-84. <https://doi.org/10.3406/carav.2001.1285>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 500 BCE - 1519 CE

Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

— Yes

Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

— Field doesn't know

Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

— Yes

Notes: There are two reliefs that depict the mythological feathered serpent, and may be interpreted as a kind of mythological narrative. The earliest case is the clay relief on the Plataforma de los Chapulincitos; it probably measured 31 meters long. A later case is the Altar 2 (4.23 by 3.97 meters), whose edges are carved with two intertwined feathered rattlesnakes. In both cases, there are "scrolls" that frame and overlap the serpents, and these used to be symbols that frame sacred spaces in other places like Teotihuacan, Monte Albán and Ixcaquixtla (popoloca region of Puebla).

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 BCE - 600 CE

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

— No

↳ Other [Specify]

— Other [specify]: Royal authority and sacredness symbols

Notes: Edificio F: mat reliefs The panels of the Edificio F were made of large stone blocks carved in a mat design. This motif evokes the idea of royalty and majesty, because the mat is associated with the ruler's throne. Edificios 3 y 4: "T" design The southern side of the acropolis of the Great Pyramid seems to have had a particular decoration program (different from the other sides): the facades of many buildings present curved slopes with "T"-shaped volumes supporting the tableros. This feature has been interpreted as an evocation of the concept of the sacred cave (inside the mountain).

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio, ed.. Proyecto Cholula. Edited by Ignacio Marquina. Serie De Investigaciones No.19. México: INAH, 1970.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 350 CE - 6 CE

↳ Are there paintings present:

— Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

— No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

— Yes

Notes: Unlike sculpture, wall/mural painting appears to have been the preferred medium for expressing elite concepts and statements in Cholula.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 BCE - 600 CE

↳ Type

— Secco

Notes: The paintings were made on plastered surfaces made of clay with stucco and/or gravels, whose surface was flattened and polished.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 BCE - 600 CE

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

— Field doesn't know

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

— Yes

Notes: Mural de Los Chapulines Stage: Edificio de los Chapulines (100-150 AD) Location: on tableros of Northern facade, 6th and 7th levels Dimension: Tableros 1.76 meters high, total estimated perimeter: 169 meters Total painted area: 442.8 square meters Colors: black, red, yellow, white and green Base: flattened and polished clay with gravels plaster Composition: Fleshless human skulls (red or yellow) with bows (above) and headdress, alternating with a zoomorphic motif (possible arthropod, posterior body. Interpretation: Depiction of Underworld realm and the ancestors. Mural de Los Chapulincitos Stage: Edificio de los Chapulines (100-150 AD) Location: on tableros of

Plataforma de los Chapulincitos (10.6 meters on a side and 1.5 meters high), northern façade-northern superior terrace of Edificio de los Chapulines. Dimension: Tableros 1.04 meters high, estimated perimeter: 31.1 meters Total painted area: 43,5 square meters Colors: black, red, yellow, white and green Base: flattened and polished clay with gravels plaster, and clay frieze modeled above Composition: red human skulls with knots on each side and an elongated red wavy element on one side. Above, scrolls with a possible undulating feathered serpent (on the clay frieze). Interpretation: same artistic and conceptual program as Los Chapulines. Mural de El Jaguar Stage: Edificio de los Chapulines-Escalonado 2 (100-300 AD) Location: on tableros of Plataforma del Jaguar, area to the southeast of the acropolis Dimension: Tableros 1.1 meters high, preserved perimeter: 8 meters Total painted area: ca. 8.5 square meters (not well preserved) Colors: black, red, yellow, white and green Base: flattened and polished clay with gravels plaster Composition: two green reptile-like figures frame the figure of a feline (in yellow with possible dark spots) that presents an atypical posture. Interpretation: mythical confrontation between serpents and jaguars in a supernatural realm (probably the Underworld).

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Robles Salmerón, María Amparo. Motivación Y Cambio Culturales: Los Orígenes De La Gran Pirámide De Cholula. Cholula: Unpublished bachelor thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2007.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Los Bebedores Mural Stage: Edificio Escalonado 1 (200-250 AD) Location: Southern sector of The Great Pyramid, western flank of Patio de los Altares Type of structure: exterior wall of palace, 6 sections (because of corners) Dimension: 2.25-2.5 meters high; 62.12 meter long; middle portion (25.5 meters long) projects 3m to the front with a central vain 6 meters wide (entrance to inner room, 25 by 7 meters). The upper portion of the central part was partially destroyed by a later superstructure. Colors: red, ochre, black, yellow, blue and white Base: flattened and polished clay with gravels plaster Composition: 112 characters (most of them probably warriors) participating in a festive ceremony where they consume intoxicating drinks (pulque); they are framed with symbols that evoke war and possible heraldic emblems. Interpretation: It is unclear whether this festive ceremony depicts an actual historical event, or a traditional practice of a warriors elite. The vessels that the characters are using correspond to those found archaeologically in ritual trash pits excavated in the area occupied by the UDLAP campus.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Uruñuela y Ladrón de Guevara, Gabriela, and Patricia Plunket Nagoda. "El Mural De Los Bebedores De Cholula: Ceremonias De Embriaguez.". *Arqueología Mexicana* XIX, no. 114 (2012): 40-43.

Reference: Rodríguez, Dionisio. "The Pre-hispanic Murals of Cholula". In *Cholula, the Great Pyramid*, 131-56. México: CONACULTA, INAH and Grupo Azabache, 2006.

Reference: Salomón, Teresa, Elba Domínguez, and Gabriela Uruñuela. "Vasos Y Braseros, Cerámicas Y Rituales Del Clásico En Cholula.". In *Migración, Población, Territorio Y Cultura. Homenaje a Román Piña Chan*, edited by Julieta Aréchiga. México: SMA, IIA, UNAM, 2006.

Reference: Rodríguez Cabrera, Dionisio. "El Mural De Los Bebedores De Cholula, Puebla.". *Arqueología Mexicana* XI, no. 59 (2003): 32-37.

Reference: Plunket, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela. "Evidence of Ancient Lifeways". In *Cholula. The Great Pyramid*, 157-76. México: CONACULTA, INAH and Grupo Azabache, 2006.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 250 CE

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Bands, stars and mat-motif

Notes: The artistic program on the south side of the Great Pyramid included a large number of talud-tablero platforms (edificios 3 and 4) with murals decorating the

panels. An important part of them presents compositions of diagonal bands with stars. During the Early Classic, the five-pointed stars indicated water; the colored bands, as seen in later Mixtec codices, indicated stone; thus, together as "the water, the mountain" constituted the Nahuatl diphthong "altepetl" that connotes a community with its authority, that is, a city-state with a temple and a palace. By adding the "T" motifs of the lower slopes that evoke the sacred cave, this reinforced the concept of altepetl and probably was a proclamation of Cholula as a sacred place where different levels of the cosmos were connected. Another feature that appears on the tableros is the mat-motif. As explained for the Edificio F, this design evokes the royal authority.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia. "El Patio De Los Altares En La Gran Pirámide De Cholula: La Violenta Destrucción De Los Iconos". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 42-47.

Reference: Marquina, Ignacio, ed.. *Proyecto Cholula*. Edited by Ignacio Marquina. Serie De Investigaciones No.19. México: INAH, 1970.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 BCE - 600 CE

- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Art, crafts, and architecture

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 1519 CE

- ↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - Yes
 - Notes: Examples: Possible arthropod: Mural de Los Chapulines Serpents and jaguars: Mural de El Jaguar Feathered serpent: Mural de Los Chapulincitos (frieze), Altar 2 Reptile (possibly serpent): Escultura de Xiuhtli Toad (on the Tlachihualtépetl): Historia Tolteca Chihimeca, folios 14r y 27r.
- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: The Great Pyramid includes many depictions that draw links with the Underworld, the realm of afterlife. Los Chapulines could be considered a graphic window to the conception of the Underworld (dark, where the dead and dark beings live). Likewise, the scene of the mural of El Jaguar occurs in a dark environment, probably also related to the Underworld. Furthermore, references to the “sacred cave” on the southern side of the acropolis reinforce this references.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 600 CE

→ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: The Tláloc-vessels could be considered here, with the iconography of the storm god. Some fragments of this type of vessels were found in the excavations of the filled cavities on the UDLAP campus, as well as figurines and effigy censers that could also be considered here.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Mauricio Gómez, Natalia. Celebraciones Y Parafernalia Ritual En Cinco Basureros Del Formativo Terminal-clásico Temprano En Cholula.. Cholula: Unpublished master's thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2010.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 50 CE - 350 CE

→ Humans

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Humans (in the Mural de Los Bebedores) appear with loincloths, elaborate hairstyles (the hair is indicated with parallel lines), earmuffs (probably denote status), some have their bodies painted with a distinctive color; others have zoomorphic features, such as one with a bird's beak (perhaps a mask). The rhombuses with scrolls have been interpreted as the juxtaposition of “fire” and “water”, meaning war. The round elements could be the emblem of some social group.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 300 CE

→ Supernatural narratives

– Field doesn't know

→ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: There is not enough evidence to affirm whether the festive ceremony, represented in the Mural de los Bebedores, corresponds to a real historical event or a traditional practice of the warriors. However, it seems very likely that celebrations of this type took place, since the vessels used by the characters correspond to those found archaeologically in ritual trash pits excavated in the area occupied by the UDLAP campus.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Uruñuela y Ladrón de Guevara, Gabriela, and Patricia Plunket Nagoda. “El Mural De Los Bebedores De Cholula: Ceremonias De Embriaguez.”. *Arqueología Mexicana* XIX, no. 114 (2012): 40-43.

Reference: Salomón, Teresa, Elba Domínguez, and Gabriela Uruñuela. “Vasos Y Braseros, Cerámicas Y Rituales Del Clásico En Cholula.”. In *Migración, Población, Territorio Y Cultura. Homenaje a Román Piña Chan*, edited by Julieta Aréchiga. México: SMA, IIA, UNAM, 2006.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 300 CE

→ Other [Specify]

—Other [specify]: Scrolls or volutes

Notes: Scrolls appear since the earliest stages of the Great Pyramid (frieze of the Plataforma de los Capulincitos) and are used to frame sacred spaces. In the case of the altares (1, 2 y 3) the scrolls has also been interpreted as the diphrasism "pocltli, ayajuitl" meaning "smoke, fog", which meaning evokes the glory of the ruler.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia. "El Patio De Los Altares En La Gran Pirámide De Cholula: La Violenta Destrucción De Los Iconos". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 42-47.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 BCE - 600 CE

—Yes

Notes: The Polychrome Ceramics (Mixteca-Puebla style) The Mixteca-Puebla style is an artistic style that characterized an important group of polychrome vessels dating from 1250 to 1521 AD in Central and South Mexico. This ceramic has been classified by Noguera, Lind and McCafferty; recently, relevant iconographic and iconological studies have been carried out by Rojas and Hernández (their work is the reference study here). The decoration of these vessels features a standardized set of geometric and detailed motifs, as well as a precise use of color. The pictography is iconic, ideographic and even metaphorical, which made possible the transmission of complex (ritual and historical) information in a systematic way during the Postclassic. This ceramic is also called codex-type because they use the same representation technique as the Mixtec codices and those of the Borgia group. The painted motifs were signs that represented objects and actions (rituals). The images followed a code of conventions that allowed messages to be transmitted (without being phonetic), and the images did not always indicate the particular use of the vessel, but rather its link with certain practices. The signs tend to appear more than once around the vessel and frequently in pairs (diphrasisms). The study of these vessels proposes that they not only followed conventions of language and ceremonial writing, but also reproduced the structure of the Mesoamerican worldview and ritual practice, which was structured on fundamental oppositions such as light-darkness. Several complexes of signs have been identified. They refer to ritual activities in general or certain types of ceremonies. In any case, the signs are not intended to present in a naturalistic or direct manner the objects they represent, but rather constitute a kind of abbreviation or metaphor for ritual and ceremonial discourses. During the early Postclassic (1150-1350 AD), the polychrome vessels from Cholula depicts the Early Postclassic International Symbol Set (e.g. geometric motifs and signs like step-frets, solar disks, feathered serpents) and the Complex of Sun and Light (eagles, hummingbirds, other birds, red circles). The late polychromes (1350-1550 AD), known as codex-style vessels, seem to group into a dual notion of light and darkness, including the complexes of: Solar Band, Powerful Lords and Deities, Vessels for Pulque, Flowers, Whorship of Ancestors, Propitiating Agricultural Fertility, Darkness. No calendric dates, toponyms, nor personal names are identified.

Reference: Hernández Sanchez, Gilda . "Vasijas De Luz Y De Oscuridad: La Cerámica Tipo Códice Del Estilo Mixteca-puebla". *Itinerarios*, no. 8 (2008): 113-27. <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=5744260>.

Reference: Hernández Sanchez, Gilda . "El Estilo Mixteca-puebla Y La Cerámica Policromada De Cholula: La Loza En Que Comía Moctezuma". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 54-59.

Reference: Hernández Sanchez, Gilda . *Vasijas Para Ceremonia. Iconografía De La Cerámica Tipo Códice Del Estilo Mixteca-puebla*. Leiden: CNWS and Leiden University , 2005.

Reference: Rojas Martínez Gracida, Araceli, and Gilda Hernández Sánchez. "Writing and Ritual: The Transformation to Mixteca-puebla Ceramics of Cholula". *Americae [on Line]* 4 (2019): 47-70. <https://americae.fr/articles/writing-ritual-transformation-mixteca-puebla-ceramics-cholula/>.

Reference: Solís, Felipe, and Verónica Velasquez. "The Polychrome Ceramics from Cholula and Other Sites in the Valleys of Puebla.". In *Cholula, the Great Pyramid*, 79-130. México: CONACULTA, INAH and Grupo Azabache, 2006.

Reference: Noguera, Eduardo. *La Cerámica Arqueológica De Cholula*. México: Editorial Guaranía, 1954.

Reference: Lind, Michael . "Cholula and Mixteca Polychromes: Two Mixteca-puebla Regional Sub-styles". In *Mixteca-puebla*, edited by Henry Nicholson and Eloise Quiñones Keber, 79-99. Culver City: Laberynthos, 1994.

Reference: McCafferty, Geoffrey. *Ceramics of Postclassic Cholula, Mexico*. Monograph 43. Los Angeles: University of California Press and The Cotsen Institute of Archaeology, 2001.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1150 CE - 1521 CE

→ Eyes (stylized or not)

—Yes

Notes: Stellar eyes, and dislocated eyes.

Reference: Rojas Martínez Gracida, Araceli, and Gilda Hernández Sánchez. "Writing and Ritual: The Transformation to Mixteca-puebla Ceramics of Cholula". *Americae* [on Line] 4 (2019): 47-70. <https://americae.fr/articles/writing-ritual-transformation-mixteca-puebla-ceramics-cholula/>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1250 BCE - 1521 CE

Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Depicted animals (remember that they constitute a kind of abbreviation or metaphor of more complex concepts): Eagles, hummingbirds, and other unidentified birds associated with feathers Feathers, bird heads Serpents, feathered serpents, fire serpents Monkey, or being with monkey attributes Jaguars Scorpions Butterflies

Reference: Rojas Martínez Gracida, Araceli, and Gilda Hernández Sánchez. "Writing and Ritual: The Transformation to Mixteca-puebla Ceramics of Cholula". *Americae* [on Line] 4 (2019): 47-70. <https://americae.fr/articles/writing-ritual-transformation-mixteca-puebla-ceramics-cholula/>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1250 BCE - 1521 CE

Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Signs associated with earth-sky: Celestial and terrestrial bands Patterns of diamonds (dried earth) Sun (red circles)

Reference: Rojas Martínez Gracida, Araceli, and Gilda Hernández Sánchez. "Writing and Ritual: The Transformation to Mixteca-puebla Ceramics of Cholula". *Americae* [on Line] 4 (2019): 47-70. <https://americae.fr/articles/writing-ritual-transformation-mixteca-puebla-ceramics-cholula/>.

Reference: Rojas Martínez Gracida, Araceli. "La Iconografía E Iconología Relacionada Con El Sol En Los Policromos Silvia Y Diana De Cholula". *Arqueología* 37 (2008): 140-54. <https://revistas.inah.gob.mx/index.php/arqueologia/article/view/3688>.

Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Gods are mentioned but in a metaphorical and simplified manner by means of their attributes: Xipe, Xochiquetzal, Quetzalcoatl (shell-jewels), Chicomecoatl, Xochipilli, Macuixochitl, Tonacatecuhli, Tezcatlipoca, Mixcoatl, Tlahuizcalpantecuhli, Cinteotl

Reference: Rojas Martínez Gracida, Araceli, and Gilda Hernández Sánchez. "Writing and Ritual: The Transformation to Mixteca-puebla Ceramics of Cholula". *Americae* [on Line] 4 (2019): 47-70. <https://americae.fr/articles/writing-ritual-transformation-mixteca-puebla-ceramics-cholula/>.

Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Yes

Notes: Geometric and abstract motifs: Step-fret motif Animated flints

Reference: Rojas Martínez Gracida, Araceli, and Gilda Hernández Sánchez. "Writing and Ritual: The Transformation to Mixteca-puebla Ceramics of Cholula". *Americae* [on Line] 4 (2019): 47-70. <https://americae.fr/articles/writing-ritual-transformation-mixteca-puebla-ceramics-cholula/>.

Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: Elements associated with the death realm: Skull and crossed bones Iconography of death

Reference: Rojas Martínez Gracida, Araceli, and Gilda Hernández Sánchez. "Writing and Ritual: The Transformation to Mixteca-puebla Ceramics of Cholula". *Americae* [on Line] 4 (2019): 47-70. <https://americae.fr/articles/writing-ritual-transformation-mixteca-puebla-ceramics-cholula/>.

Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Pan-mesoamerican belief system and ritual practice.

↳ Humans

— Yes

Notes: Human traits: faces, skulls, old human faces, blood (ofering), lungs, hands, hearts, vertebras Entertainers Warriors

Reference: Rojas Martínez Gracida, Araceli, and Gilda Hernández Sánchez. "Writing and Ritual: The Transformation to Mixteca-puebla Ceramics of Cholula". *Americae* [on Line] 4 (2019): 47-70. <https://americae.fr/articles/writing-ritual-transformation-mixteca-puebla-ceramics-cholula/>.

Reference: Rojas Martínez Gracida, Araceli . "Los Entretenedores En Los Policromos Del Tipo Albina De Cholula: Una Propuesta Iconográfica.". *Arqueología* 39 (2008): 77-92. <https://revistas.inah.gob.mx/index.php/arqueologia/article/view/3574>.

↳ Supernatural narratives

— Yes

Notes: The vessels were part of the ritual performance to communicate with gods.

Reference: Rojas Martínez Gracida, Araceli, and Gilda Hernández Sánchez. "Writing and Ritual: The Transformation to Mixteca-puebla Ceramics of Cholula". *Americae* [on Line] 4 (2019): 47-70. <https://americae.fr/articles/writing-ritual-transformation-mixteca-puebla-ceramics-cholula/>.

↳ Human narratives

— Yes

Notes: The vessels transmitted complex historical messages or narratives, and discourses about beauty, nobility, luxury.

Reference: Rojas Martínez Gracida, Araceli, and Gilda Hernández Sánchez. "Writing and Ritual: The Transformation to Mixteca-puebla Ceramics of Cholula". *Americae* [on Line] 4 (2019): 47-70. <https://americae.fr/articles/writing-ritual-transformation-mixteca-puebla-ceramics-cholula/>.

↳ Other [Specify]

— Other [specify]: Other related to rituals and ceremonies

Notes: Jades Chalchihuites War (water and fire, shields, flags, crossed arrows, red shields) Ritual calendar Four interlaced volutes Speech volutes Red circles (sun) Sun rays Sacrificial tools: bone awls, agave thorns Flowers Maiz cobs Smoke (scrolls) Precious stones Mirrors

Reference: Rojas Martínez Gracida, Araceli, and Gilda Hernández Sánchez. "Writing and Ritual: The Transformation to Mixteca-puebla Ceramics of Cholula". *Americae* [on Line] 4 (2019): 47-70. <https://americae.fr/articles/writing-ritual-transformation-mixteca-puebla-ceramics-cholula/>.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

— No

Notes: Cholula was an ancient city populated during ca. 24 centuries. Therefore, burials are important evidence of this settlement. Archaeologists have found graves and burials within or associated with domestic compounds, and also as offerings inside altar-like structures, for example. At site R-106 (archaeological rescue carried out by Suárez), 500 meters north of the Great Pyramid, there was a small tomb made of slabs under the latest stuccoed floor of a house. It contained two individuals. Tombs are not typical for Cholula during the Classic period.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Suárez Cruz, Sergio, and Silvia Martínez Arriaga. "Breve Historia De La Arqueología De Cholula, Puebla.". *Antropología. Revista Interdisciplinaria Del INAH* 78 (2005): 87-94.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

— Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

— Field doesn't know

Notes: The acropolis of the Great Pyramid exhibits many references to the Underworld from the earliest to the latest stages. The architectural and artistic programs constantly point out to references to this supernatural realm where the ancestors live. The archaeological evidence so

far does not allow us to affirm whether there was any specific worship of a deceased person or a particular ancestor, but it is a possibility that we cannot dismiss. It is possible that funeral ceremonies of the rulers or for the veneration of their relics have taken place in the spaces of the north façade of the Edificio de los Chapulines.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 900 CE

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

— Yes

Notes: Between the 12th and 14th centuries, Cholula was an important political, commercial and religious center, where the cult of Ehecatl (god of the wind) made it a very popular pilgrimage center. The figure of this god overlapped with the deity of the Toltecs (Quetzalcoatl). On the other hand, the historical-mythical character of Ce Acatl Quetzalcoatl, who would have been the first ruler of Tula, after its collapse came to Cholula, inaugurating the Toltec-Chichimeca stage in this place. The information in the sources is usually contradictory, some mention Quetzalcoatl as a warrior ruler, but in others sources he appears more like a preaching priest. Therefore, this character, within the comprehensive framework of the social creation of Mesoamerican myths and deities, is recognized as a god-man. Oversimplifying, we could say that the human character of the early Postclassic was conceptually transformed and overlapped with the earlier Mesoamerican figure of the god of the wind and the later Mexica creator god of humanity towards the later part of the period.

Reference: López Austin, Alfredo. *Hombre-dios: Religión Y Política En El Mundo Náhuatl*. 2nd ed.. México: UNAM, 2022.

Reference: Florescano, Enrique. *¿cómo Se Hace Un Dios? Creación Y Recreación De Los Dioses En Mesoamérica*. México: Penguin Random House Grupo Editorial, 2016.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Pueblos Originarios. "Manuscrito Tovar. Códice Ramírez.". Accessed 2024. <https://pueblosoriginarios.com/textos/tovar/tovar.html>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

— Yes

Notes: As we have mentioned, Quetzalcoatl is a complex figure for the Mesoamerican Postclassic, whose nature converges between a warrior-hero king (Ce Acatl Topiltzin Quetzalcoatl, king of Tula), the god Ehecatl-Quetzalcoatl (linked to the ancient Mesoamerican wind god), and the priest of the god called Quetzalcoatl and 9 Wind. The historical narratives combine myth, legend, fantasy, superstition, omen and legitimizing recreation in the different identities of these characters. With the Mexica domination of a good part of the Mesoamerican territory between 1428 and 1521, the personalities, gods and cults of Ehecatl-Quetzalcoatl became an intricate complex of practices and beliefs in this cultural area (Cholula included).

Reference: Florescano, Enrique. *¿cómo Se Hace Un Dios? Creación Y Recreación De Los Dioses En Mesoamérica*. México: Penguin Random House Grupo Editorial, 2016.

Reference: Noticonquista. "Quetzalcoatl Negro". Accessed 2024. <https://www.noticonquista.unam.mx/amoxtli/1247/1247>.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

— No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

— Yes

Notes: The "Altar Mexica" (2.20 by 2.35 meters and 0.8 meters high), located south of the Patio de los Altares; contained remains of sacrificed individuals. In the "Altar Sin Nombre", located in a plaza (17.5 meters per side, 0.5 meters high) on the Southwestern Plaza of the Great Pyramid, there was a square altar (4 by 3.22 meters) containing a dedicatory burial of human hands, a decapitated skull and vessels.

By the year 1350 the plaza was abandoned, but the area was used to bury sacrificial victims (more than 100 individuals). Both altars contained offerings (vessels, figurines) and date from the Postclassic period. The study of these remains was carried out by López, Lagunas and Serrano.

Reference: López, Sergio, Zaid Lagunas, and Carlos Serrano. Enterramientos Humanos De La Zona Arqueológica De Cholula, Puebla, INAH, México. Colección Científica 44. México: INAH, 1976.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Human:

– Yes

↳ How many humans are present:

– Number of human sacrifices: More than 100 individuals

Notes: Altar Mexica: 10 (adults and infants) Altar Sin Nombre: some inside the structure, and outside over 100 individuals (dismembered, fleshed and burned).

Reference: López, Sergio, Zaid Lagunas, and Carlos Serrano. Enterramientos Humanos De La Zona Arqueológica De Cholula, Puebla, INAH, México. Colección Científica 44. México: INAH, 1976.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know.

↳ Animal:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Almost all the burials found in Cholula (from the Formative to the Postclassic) have some type of associated offering.

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: The burial excavated by Suarez (1982) in a substructure of the open patios contained bracelets (southern zone of the Great Pyramid), a necklace, as well as 10 vessels (some like those represented in the Mural de Los Bebedores). This was a male individual probably of high status.

Reference: Suárez Cruz, Sergio. Un Entierro Del Clásico Superior En Cholula, Puebla. Cuaderno De Trabajo, No. 6. México: Centro Regional de Puebla INAH, 1985.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 BCE - 600 CE

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

Notes: Several buried individuals had a green bead as part of their grave goods.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

Notes: Most burials contain at least one and others more than 30 vessels. Those vessels must have contained offerings (many perishable) and may have been associated with the individual while he/s was alive.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Figurines (ceramic or stone), animal and human bones, musical instruments, obsidian blades, ornaments, jewelery

Notes: The type of offering depended on the personality of the individual (status, gender, age, occupation).

> Other

–Yes [specify]: Vessels,

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: The number of burials found in Cholula does not correspond to the population that must have inhabited the place for more than 20 centuries. Surely there were various alternative practices to burial, such as cremation, which must have been very common.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

> As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: In general, there are no documented cemeteries as such. However, there are places with important concentrations of burials such as that around the "Altar Sin Nombre" and another further southeast of the archaeological zone. Both represent human remains deposit areas, and date to the period after the structures were abandoned.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

Notes: There are two sites that may be considered here. The first is the small tomb made of slabs at the R-126 site (described above). The second would be the Altar de los Cráneos Esculpidos found in a complex of residences and patios on the northeastern area of the Great Pyramid. It is located in the center of a sunken patio (900-1150 AD), and it is a platform about 2 meters per side and 60cm high with a staircase; it has a clay and stucco skull built in on each side. Inside, the skeletons of a woman and a man were found, both with offerings. The staircase presents a perforation with two ceramic tubes that connect to the inside.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Lagunas Rodríguez, Zaid. El Altar De Los Cráneos Esculpidos De Cholula. Una Interpretación Antropológica. México: El Errante editor, 2012.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1150 CE

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

— Yes

Notes: According to tradition from the Formative period, people used to bury their dead, or at least those important ancestors, inside their houses or residences. In the southern and western area of the Great Pyramid, a large number of burials (more than 440), with a diversity of mortuary treatments, were excavated. This indicates the presence of residences that were covered by subsequent stages of the Great Pyramid. Similar cases were found in the UDLAP campus (25 individuals) and in INAH salvage excavations (e.g. 76 burials in 2009) on the streets of the modern city of Cholula; these clusters of burials also point to houses that no longer exist. Mansilla studied the human bone material obtained in the Proyecto Cholula between 1966 and 1971; she concluded that the Cholultecas lived in poor cultural biological conditions, but these were better than those of the Tlatelolcas in the Basin of Mexico.

Reference: Uruñuela, Gabriela, and Patricia Plunket. "Lineages and Ancestors. The Formative Mortuary Assemblages of Tetimpa, Puebla." In *Domestic Ritual in Ancient Mesoamerica*, Monograph 6:20–30. Los Angeles: The Cotsen Institut of Archaeology, UCLA, 1998.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Romero Butrón, Ashuni, and Carlos Cedillo Ortega. "Excavando En Las Calles De Cholula: El Reto Del Progreso." *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 74–75.

Reference: Mansilla Lory, Josefina. *Las Condiciones Biológicas De La Población Prehispánica De Cholula, Puebla. Estudio De Las Líneas De Harris*. Vol. 82. Colección Científica. México: SEP, INAH, 1980.

Reference: Suárez Cruz, Sergio. *Últimos Descubrimientos De Entierros Posclásicos En Cholula, Puebla. Cuaderno De Trabajo, No. 7*. México: Centro Regional de Puebla INAH, 1989.

Reference: Müller, Florencia. *La Alfarería De Cholula. Serie Arqueología*. México: INAH, SEP, 1978.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Other

—Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

— Yes

Notes: As mentioned, Ehécatl-Quetzalcóatl was the central god in the Postclassic city of Cholula.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

— Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

— Yes

Notes: His dimension as Ehécatl (god of wind) may have a celestial connotation.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

— Yes

Notes: Qutezalcoatl in the Nahua tradition was one of the gods that were involved in the creation of the world. He brought the human race to life through his sacrifice and overcoming of some challenges in the Underworld.

Reference: Florescano, Enrique. *¿cómo Se Hace Un Dios? Creación Y Recreación De Los Dioses En Mesoamérica.* México: Penguin Random House Grupo Editorial, 2016.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

- ↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
 - No
- ↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are they unquestionably good:
 - No
- ↳ Are they other:
 - Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ In dreams:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The two high priests who directed the ritual-religious practice in Postclassic Cholula, where the cult of Quetzalcóatl was essential, were the Tlalquiach and the AQUIACH.
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: None

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned, in the Postclassic period the "nature" of Quetzalcoatl was complex, being a combination of myth, legend and history. The god had diverse dimensions as supernatural being but also as man/king/hero/priest.

Reference: Florescano, Enrique. *¿cómo Se Hace Un Dios? Creación Y Recreación De Los Dioses En Mesoamérica..* México: Penguin Random House Grupo Editorial, 2016.

Reference: López Austin, Alfredo. *Hombre-dios: Religión Y Política En El Mundo Náhuatl..* 2nd ed. México: UNAM, 2022.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As mentioned before, the idol of Quetzalcoatl was kept inside the chamber of his temple (according historical sources). It was visible to his priests and probably also to important dignitaries who visited the temple to present gifts and offerings.

Reference: Durán, Diego. *Ritos Y Fiestas De Los Antiguos Mexicanos*. México: Editorial Innovación, 1980.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: During the Classic period, the acropolis of the Great Pyramid was the focus of worship in the city. Large-scale public ceremonies should have occurred in plazas surrounding or above the acropolis. The architectural programs throughout the construction sequence show that ritual practice was integrated into various sectors of the acropolis itself, which was the most important building in the central precinct. The different plazas and terraces of each stage are evidence of a diversified and integrative ritual practice. As the city grew, the needs and scale of these practices probably expanded, creating spaces that could accommodate up to 7,500 people as the Patio de los Altares, or 25,000 people in the projected western esplanade of the Edificio de los Tableros Lisos. For the Postclassic period, we do not know what the size of the Great Plaza of Cholula was, but it is very likely that there were large spaces with similar function. Ceremonial practices of an intermediate level (family and the state) were identified in the filling of the cavities on the UDLAP campus. There, artifacts for festive and ritual use were found (vases, obsidian points, braziers, figurines and "Tlálloc" vessels), which do not correspond to domestic activities, but it may point to ritual feasts or banquets.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. *Cholula*. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Reference: Uruñuela, Gabriela, Patricia Plunket, and María Amparo Robles. "Cholula: Art and Architecture of an Archetypal City." In *The Art of Urbanism: How Mesoamerican Kingdoms Represented Themselves in Architecture and Imagery*, edited by William L. Fash and Leonardo López Luján, 135-71. Washington DC: Dumbarton Oaks, 2009.

Reference: Mauricio Gómez, Natalia. *Celebraciones Y Parafernalia Ritual En Cinco Basureros Del Formativo Terminal-clásico Temprano En Cholula*. Cholula: Unpublished master's thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2010.

Reference: Salomón, Teresa, Elba Domínguez, and Gabriela Uruñuela. "Vasos Y Braseros, Cerámicas Y Rituales Del Clásico En Cholula." In *Migración, Población, Territorio Y Cultura. Homenaje a Román Piña Chan*, edited by Julieta Aréchiga. México: SMA, IIA, UNAM, 2006.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Smaller-scale rituals probably took place at various levels, such as the ancestors worship (at least at the domestic level), as well as funerary rituals (evidenced in burials of commoners). Furthermore, a wide variety of rituals of a more private and exclusive level must have taken place either in the temples and plazas/patios of the acropolis, or in the buildings or the Great Plaza (including the Temple of Quetzalcoatl) or in those temples dedicated to minor deities that were mentioned as "towers" by the Europeans who described Cholula.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Field does not know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Field does not know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: The Mural de los Bebedores suggests that the consumption of intoxicating beverages like pulque (on specific occasions) could be part of an ancestral tradition linked to specific social groups (e.g., elders and warriors).

Reference: Uruñuela y Ladrón de Guevara, Gabriela, and Patricia Plunket Nagoda. "El Mural De Los Bebedores De Cholula: Ceremonias De Embriaguez.". *Arqueología Mexicana* XIX, no. 114 (2012): 40-43.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 250 CE

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned previously, there are some sites where the deposit of remains of people who were apparently sacrificed was documented (Altar Mexica and Altar Sin Nombre), but there is not much more archaeological information about this kind of practices. In historical sources such as the Historia Tolteca Chichimeca and the Mapa de Cuauhtinchan 2, some sacrificial practices that took place in Cholula are documented and these were performed as a consequence of the victory of the Chichimecas allied to the Toltecs. These were probably of a martial type: sacrifice with arrows tlacacaliztli (the victim was tied to a scaffold-type structure and was shot with arrows until he bled to death), gladiatorial sacrifice on a quauhtmalacatl or stone disc (the prisoner had to fight with a blunt weapon). Associated with these events, another type of sacrifice appears recorded on the Map of Cuauhtinchan 2. This happens in front of the temple of Quetzalcoatl: two Toltec warriors or priests decapitate a grasshopper and a butterfly, and apparently, they are going to offer an eagle and a snake, which are held by the two men. This type of sacrifice appears to be a Chichimec practice that is associated with the type of blood sacrifice performed by Topiltzin Quetzalcoatl.

Reference: Boone, Elizabeth H. "The House of the Eagle". In *Cave, City, and Eagle's Nest*, edited by David Carrasco and Scott Sessions. Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press, 2007.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. *Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas*, 2018.

Reference: Pueblos Originarios. "Anales De Cuauhtinchan. Historia Totlteca-chichimeca.". Accessed 2024. <https://pueblosoriginarios.com/meso/valle/tolteca/anales.html>.

Reference: Tlachia UNAM. "Cuauhtinchan 2". Tlachia. *Contenidos pictográficos del Náhuatl*, 2012. <https://tlachia.iib.unam.mx/cuauhtinchan-2/MC2>.

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

–Yes [specify]: Grasshoper, butterfly, and maybe eagle and serpent.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

–Yes

Reference: López, Sergio, Zaid Lagunas, and Carlos Serrano. Enterramientos Humanos De La Zona Arqueológica De Cholula, Puebla, INAH, México.. Colección Científica 44. México: INAH, 1976.

↳ Adults

–Yes

↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:

–Male

–Female

↳ Children

–Yes

↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:

–Other/InD

↳ Foreigners and/or slaves

–Field doesn't know

↳ Elites

–Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: None

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

–Yes [specify]: Ritual practice

Notes: The remains of those sacrificed on the Altar Mexica and the Altar Sin Nombre suggest that human sacrifice was part of the ritual practice in the Postclassic city.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

–Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:

–Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

–Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

–Yes

↳ Is it required:

–Field doesn't know

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The architectural sequence of the acropolis of the Great Pyramid is an important evidence about this aspect.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 900 CE

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

Notes: After the transition from the Classic to the Postclassic, Cholula seems to be an important pilgrimage center, although it may have been so since the Classic period. Many of the visitors came from very distant lands or kingdoms. They arrived with rich offerings, and took advantage of the trip to sell and buy in the great market (hueytianquitzli). It should be located west of the Great Plaza. Every 52 years the people of the kingdoms that had kings confirmed in Cholula made a great pilgrimage to that city, to deliver offerings of feathers, blankets, silver, gold and precious stones to the Temple of Quetzalcoatl.

Reference: Merlo Juárez, Eduardo. "Cholula, La Roma De Mesoamérica". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 24-30.

Reference: de Rojas, Gabriel. "Relación De Cholula (1581)". In *Relaciones Geográficas Del Siglo XVI*, edited by René Acuña, Tomo II:121-45. México: UNAM, 1984.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

↳ Birth

– Field doesn't know

↳ Transition to adulthood

– Field doesn't know

↳ Death

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Confirmation of kings/lords

Notes: In the "casilla especial", located north of the Great Plaza, the two high priests of Cholula (Tlalchiach and Aquiach) confirmed foreign rulers in their position by piercing

their nose, lobes or lower lip to place a jewel that was the insignia of their royalty. The kings fasted for four days before the ceremony.

Reference: Hermann Lejarazu, Manuel A. . "Códice Nuttall. Lado 1: La Vida De 8 Venado". *Arqueología Mexicana Edición Especial*, no. 23 (2007).

Reference: Lind, Michael, and Catalina Barrientos. "Así Era La Gran Plaza De Tollancholollan". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 48-53.

Reference: Pueblos Originarios. "Anales De Cuauhtinchan. Historia Totlteca-chichimeca.". Accessed 2024.

<https://pueblosoriginarios.com/meso/valle/tolteca/anales.html>.

Reference: Kirchoff, Paul, Lina Odena, and Luis Reyes García. *Historia Tolteca-chichimeca*. México: INAH, 1976.

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Feasting and ritual feasting should have been common at the city during its different occupations. The archeological evidence in the UDLAP campus (cavities containing artifacts from a feasting and/or banquet) support this idea. The Mural de los Bebedores depicts very clearly one of them, although it is not clear if there was any link to sacrifices or any specific religious cult or practice.

Reference: Mauricio Gómez, Natalia. *Celebraciones Y Parafernalia Ritual En Cinco Basureros Del Formativo Terminal-clásico Temprano En Cholula*. Cholula: Unpublished master's thesis, Departamento de Antropología, UDLAP, 2010.

Reference: Uruñuela y Ladrón de Guevara, Gabriela, and Patricia Plunket Nagoda. "El Mural De Los Bebedores De Cholula: Ceremonias De Embriaguez.". *Arqueología Mexicana* XIX, no. 114 (2012): 40-43.

Reference: Salomón, Teresa, Elba Domínguez, and Gabriela Uruñuela. "Vasos Y Braseros, Cerámicas Y Rituales Del Clásico En Cholula.". In *Migración, Población, Territorio Y Cultura. Homenaje a Román Piña Chan*, edited by Julieta Aréchiga. México: SMA, IIA, UNAM, 2006.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 550 CE

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

Notes: It is very likely.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 BCE - 1519 CE

↳ Priests

– Yes

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: It is likely that the offerings of pilgrims to the Temple of Quetzalcoatl and local taxes financed this type of ceremonial practices.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Other

—Other [specify]: Fiel doesn't know.

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

—Yes [specify]: Palace

Notes: In the case of the Mural de Los Bebedores, it seems likely that the celebration depicted there took place in the same building that decorates the mural. In this case, probably it is a palace.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 250 CE

Are festivals present:

—Field doesn't know

Notes: Cholula was a city with many temples dedicated to different patron deities, according to historical sources like Bernal Díaz. Each of them must have had their respective festivals and ceremonies. Although the archaeological evidence and historical information is limited, it is likely that those celebrations were frequent and sumptuous.

Reference: Merlo Juárez, Eduardo. "Cholula, La Roma De Mesoamérica". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 24-30.

Reference: Díaz del Castillo, Bernal. *Historia Verdadera De La Conquista De La Nueva España*. México: Editorial Patria, 1983.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

—Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

—Field doesn't know

Notes: A "T" shaped platform was exposed 350 meters west of the Great Pyramid (on 3 Oriente Street), and it has skulls and crossed long bones modeled on it. These symbols are linked to the Tzizimine. In Nahua mythology, these dark supernatural beings were associated with illness and healing. In the Tudela Codex (f.76) it can be observed that a Tzizimine stands on a similar platform and is fed with blood.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

—Yes

Notes: Postclassic Cholula functioned as a religious center and capital of a señorío. The two high priests who headed the government (Tlalchiach and Aquiach) regulated relations with the outer kingdoms and provinces, a general captain was in charge of the army (Chichimecatl teuctli), and a council of six nobles administered the señorío at the local level. These levels of government were closely articulated and converged in the Great Plaza of the city.

Reference: Lind, Michael. "La Gran Cuadra De La Ciudad: El Gobierno Prehispánico De Cholula". *Arqueología* 39 (2008): 65-76.

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Reference: Pueblos Originarios. "Anales De Cuauhtinchan. Historia Totlteca-chichimeca.". Accessed 2024. <https://pueblosoriginarios.com/meso/valle/tolteca/anales.html>.

Reference: Lind, Michael, and Catalina Barrientos. "Así Era La Gran Plaza De Tollan-cholollan". *Arqueología Mexicana* XX, no. 115 (2012): 48-53.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Present full time

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Present part time

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

— Yes

Notes: Male

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

— Yes

Notes: The priests of Quetzalcóatl were from the Tianguisnáhuac barrio (neighborhood) from Cholula.

Reference: de Rojas, Gabriel. "Relación De Cholula (1581)". In *Relaciones Geográficas Del Siglo XVI*, edited by René Acuña, Tomo II:121-45. México: UNAM, 1984.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

— Yes

Notes: Quetzalcoatl's priests must be from the upper social class (elite).

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

— Yes

Reference: de Rojas, Gabriel. "Relación De Cholula (1581)". In *Relaciones Geográficas Del Siglo XVI*, edited by René Acuña, Tomo II:121-45. México: UNAM, 1984.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

— Yes

Notes: Priests of Quetzalcoatl completed 12 years of service, which gave them the right to wear a black-red cape. When they grew old they could wear a red cape. When one of the supreme priests died, the oldest priest with red cape became the new Aquiach or Tlalchiach and he wore the purple cape reserved for the high priests.

Reference: de Rojas, Gabriel. "Relación De Cholula (1581)". In *Relaciones Geográficas Del Siglo*

XVI, edited by René Acuña, Tomo II:121-45. México: UNAM, 1984.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:
– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The Great Plaza was the ceremonial and administrative center. It was walled and had three entrances (north, south and east). The high priests and the council of nobles (including the teuctli of Chichimécatl) occupied the residences on the east side of the Great Plaza, so that communication between them was direct and immediate.

Reference: Lind, Michael. "La Gran Cuadra De La Ciudad: El Gobierno Prehispánico De Cholula". *Arqueología* 39 (2008): 65-76.

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The Calmecac (in the souththwestern area of the Great Plaza) was the "School of nobles and priests." The priests of Quetzalcóatl had to complete 12 years of service to deserve their rank.

Reference: Lind, Michael. "La Gran Cuadra De La Ciudad: El Gobierno Prehispánico De Cholula". *Arqueología* 39 (2008): 65-76.

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The maintenance of the city was in charge of the political elite. On the one hand, the high priests controlled the foreign relations of the kingdom. The priestly organization was financed mainly with foreign funds in the form of "offerings" to the Temple of Quetzalcoatl, in addition to those of pilgrims who attended the great ceremonies. On the other hand, the council of nobles (apparently nobles from the 6 or 4 districts of the city) with the chichimecatl teuctli administered local affairs (justice, taxes, fund administration and project planning, market regulation, organization of the army). This political system was financed with taxes and the tequio (communal labor) services from the different neighborhoods (calpolli) and the towns subjected to the kingdom or señorío of Cholula.

Reference: Lind, Michael. "La Gran Cuadra De La Ciudad: El Gobierno Prehispánico De Cholula". *Arqueología* 39 (2008): 65-76.

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The interpretation of historical sources identifies a political elite that articulated a complex government for a kingdom that had a great importance beyond its borders. Below the levels of the high hierarchy (the high priests and the council of nobles) it is likely that there were officials and perhaps soldiers who constituted a kind of bureaucracy, but there is no information that confirm this. The priests of Quetzalcoatl could be considered one of those groups.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: In the 16th century, Cholula controlled a large number of towns covering a territory of around 800 square kilometers, with an approximate population of 40,000 inhabitants, in addition to another 40,000 who lived in the city. The economic resources were managed and administered by the high priests (external income) and the council of nobles (local income: from the kingdom and the province).

Reference: de Rojas, Gabriel. "Relación De Cholula (1581)". In *Relaciones Geográficas Del Siglo XVI*, edited by René Acuña, Tomo II:121-45. México: UNAM, 1984.

Reference: Lind, Michael . "La Gran Cuadra De La Ciudad: El Gobierno Prehispánico De Cholula". *Arqueología* 39 (2008): 65-76.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

Does this place lease out land:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place lease out tools:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

Notes: Few written documents are preserved from the pre-Hispanic era in Mesoamerica. From Cholula, none survived the conquest or the colonial period. However, there are probable mentions of Cholula in pre-Hispanic codices from other regions. We can mention the Tonindeye (Zouche-Nutall) and the Colombino-Becker I (Alfonso Caso), both describe historical passages from the Mixtec kingdoms, and there are references to Cholula as the "Reed Place" (Tollan), being where the tecuhtli ceremony or title recognition act (nose piercieng) took place. Other codices where Cholula is explicitly mentioned and that we have cited previously, such as the *Historia Totlteca-Chichimeca*, the *Mapa de Cuahtinchan 2* or the *Códice de Cholula*, were prepared after the arrival of the Hispanics to argue and defend indigenous privileges because of the support and recognition of the royal authority. In the Postclassic, written record systems in central Mexico were pictographic, with an extensive use of signs, symbols, and colors. Mesoamerica was always a multicultural and multilingual area and this probably allowed messages to be conveyed trans-regionally among the elites. The main language of the Postclassic was Nahuatl, and the glosses of the post-Hispanic codices have shed light on understanding the dynamics and meanings of the pre-Hispanic graphic system, taking into account that Nahuatl is a language full of

metaphors. This is expressed in the Nahuatl diphrasism "in tlilli in tlapalli" (black ink and color) meaning "writing and wisdom", which refers to the writing system of those painted books (codices), where color, signs and symbols full of meaning were used to convey complex ideas and messages.

Reference: González-Hermosillo Adam, Francisco, and Luis Reyes García. *El Códice De Cholula: La Exaltación Testimonial De Un Linaje Indio*. México: INAH, CIESAS, 2002.

Reference: Hermann Lejarazu, Manuel A. . "Códice Nuttall. Lado 1: La Vida De 8 Venado." *Arqueología Mexicana Edición Especial*, no. 23 (2007).

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Reference: Pueblos Originarios. "Códice Colombino-becker I". Accessed 2024. <https://pueblosoriginarios.com/meso/oaxaca/mixteca/colombino.html>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Are they written:

— Yes

Notes: There is no collection of formal written records for Cholula, however, postclassic polychrome ceramics could be considered a means in which the Mesoamerican pictographic writing system was captured and could endure. The manufacturers of the polychrome vessels of the Middle (1150-1350 AD) and Late Postclassic (1350-1550 AD) were specialized artists and scholars (tlacuilos) who had full knowledge of the graphic systems for historical and ritual-ceremonial communication. This graphic system can be considered part of the tlilli in tlapalli, under the native concept of icuiloa, whose meaning in Nahuatl does not distinguish between writing and painting. The vessels exhibit the same system as the codices without being copies of them. In fact, in the codices there are depicted vessels of similar shapes that contain food, pulque and cacao, and others with copal or blood. Therefore, it seems that these vessels were used in ceremonies that involved offerings, whether in festivals or in another type of ritual practice. In Cholula, the groups of signs and symbols became more complex and systematized towards the later period. The language is poetic (like the diphrasisms); they allude to central themes of religion and ritual, and to the contexts in which the vessels were used. Thus, the vessels reinforced the atmosphere of sacredness of the ritual practice for the deities or ancestors. The Cholula vessels acquired such interregional fame for their quality and beauty that even Moctezuma had vessels from Cholula to serve on his table.

Reference: Hernández Sanchez, Gilda . "Vasijas De Luz Y De Oscuridad: La Cerámica Tipo Códice Del Estilo Mixteca-puebla". *Itinerarios*, no. 8 (2008): 113-27. <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=5744260>.

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Reference: Rojas Martínez Gracida, Araceli . "Los Entretenedores En Los Policromos Del Tipo Albina De Cholula: Una Propuesta Iconográfica.". *Arqueología* 39 (2008): 77-92. <https://revistas.inah.gob.mx/index.php/arqueologia/article/view/3574>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1150 CE - 1519 CE

↳ Are they written at this place:

— Yes

Notes: The polychrome ceramics were made locally. The Cholula Codex was elaborated in the locality of Cholula between 1586 and the first half of the 17th century.

Reference: González-Hermosillo Adam, Francisco, and Luis Reyes García. *El Códice De Cholula: La Exaltación Testimonial De Un Linaje Indio*. México: INAH, CIESAS, 2002.

Reference: Rojas Martínez Gracida, Araceli, and Gilda Hernández Sánchez. "Writing and Ritual: The Transformation to Mixteca-puebla Ceramics of Cholula". *Americae [on Line]* 4 (2019): 47-70. <https://americae.fr/articles/writing-ritual-transformation-mixteca-puebla-ceramics-cholula/>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1150 CE - 1519 CE

Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Oral tradition was fundamental in the creation of ancient paintings, books or codices. These narratives were conveyed in ancient cultural centers such as the calmécac or schools of priests and nobles.

Reference: León Portilla, Miguel. *Las Inscripciones Y Los Códices Mesoamericanos En Una Historia Documental De México*. 4a ed.. Historia Documental De México 1. México: UNAM, 2013. https://historicas.unam.mx/publicaciones/publicadigital/libros/historia_documental/vol01.html.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 1519 CE

Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

Notes: A myth associated with the founding of the place where Tlachihualtepetl was built is the existence of an ancient spring that flowed underneath. This idea probably arose due to the pictographs that represent the mound associated with water currents. For this reason, some believed that the building was located on a water source. However, the research made by the Tetimpa Project of the tunnels excavated by the Cholula Project confirmed that under the first construction stage of the acropolis of the Great Pyramid (Edificio de la Olla) there is no evidence of any possible spring. But there was found several trunk-conic pits filled with sand, which indicates that there were households in that place prior to the monumental construction. At present, there is an apparent spring of water on the eastern side of the Great Pyramid or Tlachihualtepetl called "El Pocito". A chapel was built on it and healing properties are attributed to its water.

Reference: Plunket Nagoda, Patricia, and Gabriela Uruñuela Ladrón de Guevara. Cholula. México: Colegio de México, Fondo de Cultura Económica, Fideicomiso Historia de las Américas, 2018.

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 0 CE - 1519 CE

Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: It seems very likely that knowledge about the pictographic writing system was shared between the ritual specialists and those artists who manufactured the "painted books" or the codex-type polychrome ceramics.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 1519 CE

Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Field doesn't know

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